

RETROVISION: HOW AMERICA'S ICONIC SITCOMS REFLECT & YET SUBVERT
CONTEMPORARY NORMS

by

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Abstract

Television—like all other artforms—is informed by historical context; furthermore, comedy is a centuries-old medium that has used humor to uniquely convey messages to audiences. The synthesis of these elements via the situational comedy (sitcom) presents a historical lens to view the evolution of America’s societal values, especially those formed in the context of major global events. As products of their eras, the most popular American sitcoms throughout history act as a reflection of the nation’s ideals through the comedic subversion of norms. Measures of audience and critical acclaim identified the quintessential sitcoms of each decade and their three best episodes for an investigation of commentary of American values of their respective eras. Analysis suggests that many iconic sitcoms throughout the ages have used their platform to make statements on hot-button issues of the time, using comedy to portray topical issues in a more palatable way. By disarming the audience through laughter, viewers become more receptive to serious messages implied by the episode. The research presented here has implications for future endeavors; the world is living through another major historical event (the COVID-19 pandemic), so any evidence of an effect on this facet of national culture will be worthy of analysis.

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RetroVision: How America's Iconic Sitcoms Reflect and Yet Subvert Contemporary Norms

A popular quote attributed to playwright George Bernard Shaw goes, "If you want to tell people the truth, you'd better make them laugh or they'll kill you". In addition, poet Francis Harvey Green once said, "Once you get them laughing and their mouths open, you can stuff anything in". Therefore by combining these two, a new aphorism can be created that demonstrates the power of humor in disseminating a message: "Get the audience laughing. While their mouths are open, stick the truth in". Comedy is a genre that has persisted for thousands of years, its origins dating back to the ancient Greeks (Rusten, 2006). On the other hand, television is a much more recent, yet still revolutionary invention that connected Americans across the nation beginning in the mid-twentieth century, allowing them to experience visual entertainment simultaneously on a mass scale similar to the way that the radio did so for auditory entertainment. Combining the two results in the situational comedy (sitcom): a genre of programming that focuses on a single group of characters that carry over from episode to episode, which revolve around a different situation each time (Provost, 2022). Sitcoms have been a staple of American television for its entire history, with iconic shows such as *I Love Lucy* contributing to its value as a facet of national culture. Seeing that the medium is dependent on societal reactions in order for success (i.e., audiences must like and connect with the content in order for the show to continue), it can be argued that history plays a rather large role in determining the state of society at a given point in time through the way it is portrayed in art. This provides a foundation on which television can react to society by dramatizing it, often taking the opportunity to disguise unpleasant truths as comedy in hopes that audiences will receive the underlying message.

In this thesis I argue that the most iconic American sitcoms act as a reflection of American society through its commentary and subversion of norms, particularly in response to major historical events. Analysis of these shows reveal a cyclical relationship between history, society, and television. First, a major historical event occurs; then, society reacts to it in a way that establishes a set of norms that dictate what is and is not okay. Sitcoms then reflect society through its portrayal on the small screen, often commenting on the state of affairs and either reinforcing or subverting them. The most iconic sitcoms influence society to the point of reaction again, allowing for the evolution of these norms usually with the help of another major historical event. Thus the cycle begins again. I have identified four major historical events since the popularity boom of the television (in the early 1950s) and demonstrate how these staples of pop culture are historical products of their time by analyzing how they reflect societal ideals and values. Doing so gives an interesting perspective into the social history of the United States and how we as Americans channel our inner reactions to current events into art. The research presented here also has additional applications to other genres of television as well as the future, given that the United States is currently living through another major historical event, the COVID-19 pandemic.

Literature Review

There is little literature that discusses the breadth of the research of this thesis due to how specific its parameters are. To reiterate their specificity, television's most iconic sitcoms are to be analyzed in the context of major historical events for any commentary on societal norms. Few comprehensive works on the evolution of television exist, such as Erik Barnouw's (1990) *Tube of Plenty*, but my initial preparation turned up nothing more recent. Some have analyzed the effect of certain historical events on comedy as a whole, such as Gournelos and Greene (2011) had

done for the September 11 attacks, however their research encompasses the genre broadly, including late night television and internet memes rather than focusing solely on sitcoms. Other authors have analyzed certain shows and their place in history; for example Garner (2002) discusses sitcoms among other television events (such as late-night shows, news, and sporting events) and their status as iconic moments or historical inspirations on shows. The New York Film Academy (2014) has a pair of articles detailing the brief evolution of the sitcom in a very similar way to how my analyses were conducted, in the sense that it mentions the most iconic shows of history. However, these were done from a more technical standpoint, focusing on production methods rather than placing them within historical context. I have yet to see a comprehensive analysis throughout history of the role of sitcoms specifically in society, particularly *in response to specific global events*. The findings presented here are also largely dependent on my own analyses after viewing specific episodes; supplemental observations are supported by authors with deep knowledge of these specific shows. All in all, the resulting thesis has been cobbled together using primarily personal analysis and additional references to works that analyze these series as a whole, offering a more holistic context in which its iconic episodes aired. The time span is large, encompassing all of television history yet focusing on one of its biggest facets, while grounding it in historical context that is much-needed to understand their consequences on American society as a whole.

Methods

The process of choosing which sitcoms most reflected the decades that they aired during was exhaustive and comprehensive. Through rigorous cross-referencing of different metrics of audience and critic popularity, I was able to identify three TV shows to represent their respective decades. For each one, I constructed a chart (Figure 1) comprising five columns: winners of the

Primetime Emmy Award for Outstanding Comedy Series, winners of the Golden Globe Award for Best Television Series—Musical or Comedy, the top-rated comedy program of each year (according to Nielsen Media Research), IMDb rankings, and Ranker.com rankings. Through this method, I had two measures of critical acclaim (Emmy and Golden Globe winners) and three measures of audience acclaim (Nielsen ratings, IMDb ratings, and Ranker.com rankings) that I believe will yield a sample size of shows that are well-regarded and representative of each decade in the eyes of most Americans. The final selection includes the following shows: *I Love Lucy*, *The Danny Thomas Show*, and *The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet* for the 1950s; *The Dick Van Dyke Show*, *Get Smart*, and *The Addams Family* for the 1960s; *All in the Family*, *M*A*S*H*, and *The Mary Tyler Moore Show* for the 1970s; *The Cosby Show*, *The Golden Girls*, and *Cheers* for the 1980s; *Seinfeld*, *Roseanne*, and *Friends* for the 1990s; *Everybody Loves Raymond*, *The Office*, and *Arrested Development* for the 2000s; and finally *Modern Family*, *The Big Bang Theory*, and *Brooklyn Nine-Nine* for the 2010s. The only exceptions to the aforementioned list are *The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet* and *The Addams Family*, which did not appear in my initial charts; they were instead chosen for their enduring contributions to pop culture. In the case of the former, though it did not top any of the lists that I referenced, the fact that the series held the title of longest running live-action sitcom of all time (in terms of seasons, before being surpassed by *It's Always Sunny In Philadelphia* in 2020) demonstrates its status as a quintessential show of its respective era (Goldberg, 2020). The latter was chosen due to its enduring status as a concept, with adaptations across media continuing well after the original series ended its run (e.g. the 1991 live-action film duology, the 2010 Broadway musical, and the 2019 animated film franchise) (Murray, personal communication, 2022).

Figure 1

A chart constructed to identify the three quintessential sitcoms of the 1970s.

1970-1979					
	Emmy Winners by Year	IMDb 1st 10 comedies	Top Rated by Year (Nielsen)	Golden Globe Winners	Ranker.com 1st 10 comedies
0	My World and Welcome to It	M*A*S*H	Here's Lucy	The Carol Burnett Show	All in the Family
1	All in the Family S1	Three's Company	All in the Family	All in the Family	Happy Days
2	All in the Family S2	Happy Days	All in the Family	All in the Family	The Jeffersons
3	All in the Family S3	Fawlty Towers	All in the Family	All in the Family	M*A*S*H
4	M*A*S*H S2	Barney Miller	All in the Family	Rhoda	Sanford and Son
5	The Mary Tyler Moore Show S5	The Mary Tyler Moore Show	All in the Family	Barney Miller	Three's Company
6	The Mary Tyler Moore Show S6	All in the Family	Happy Days	Barney Miller	The Brady Bunch
7	The Mary Tyler Moore Show S7	WKRP in Cincinnati	Laverne and Shirley	All in the Family	Laverne and Shirley
8	All in the Family S8	Good Times	Laverne and Shirley	Taxi	The Mary Tyler Moore Show
9	Taxi S1	The Jeffersons	Three's Company	Alice Taxi	The Bob Newhart Show

Rather than simply watch these shows and analyze them, which would be far too broad and tedious in order to ensure a well-crafted analysis, I chose instead to select the three most representative episodes of each show and analyze those instead. I employed a similar procedure to the aforementioned show selection, where cross-referencing different measures of popularity yielded the three quintessential episodes of every program. Various measures of popularity were used, including curated lists from media publications (formed by journalists and media analysts) as well as audience ratings from IMDb. All of the standout episodes that I directly discuss from here on have been chosen via this method (unless stated otherwise), and are implied to be the best episodes of each series, exemplary of the show as a whole.

I opted to identify larger eras that spanned multiple decades with broader applications, rather than choosing one large historical event for each decade that its programs revolve around. The latter proved to be difficult for a few reasons; first, not all decades had their equivalents to say, 9/11; second, these themes were not limited to a single decade and often bleed into their predecessors and successors. Fewer and broader eras of interest made for a more flexible approach that allowed me to pair certain shows with certain eras based on their predominant themes; for example, though *Everybody Loves Raymond* was selected as a show representing the

2000s, its premise and themes aligned more closely with those of the 80s and 90s and was thus grouped accordingly. Society and history are filled with complexities and nuances that are far too detailed to explore in such a broad topic like this one, so rather than boiling down each decade to a monolith that may be inaccurate, after identifying these tent-pole historical eras, I selected a few specific themes to focus my analysis on.

The 50s–60s: Post-War Gender Norms and Domesticity

Historical Context

The Second World War was a period of time that was both a lifeline and burden on the United States. On one hand, the skyrocketing demand for war supplies dragged Americans out of the Great Depression that was crippling the nation; on the other, desperate times called for desperate measures as the country ran out of men to help in the defense of democracy. WWII transformed the United States for women almost overnight, with many stepping up to the challenge of replacing their husbands in the workplace or even joining them on the front lines (McEuen, 2016). American women, coming from both the household and “safely feminized” fields of employment, showed up in droves to war factories, crossing gender-defined boundaries into the “masculinized workplaces of heavy industry” (McEuen, 2016). The private sector saw a boom in “feminization” as well, with thousands of job openings not previously open to women being offered at the speed of light. Though the wartime period marked huge strides in the movement towards full gender equality and many were willing to cling to the opportunities offered to them, in the eyes of the US government and the nation’s private sector, this era was merely an outlier. Their foremost message was that these were special conditions and that both sacrifices and opportunities would end once the war did. This emphasis on a push back into the familiar sphere of female domesticity proved prevalent in popular television of the time. These

ideas have stood the test of time, with many people's ideas of the 1950s include the well-entrenched stereotype of the quintessential suburban housewife, a devoted homemaker and doting wife to the working husband (Meyerowitz, 1994). It is worth noting that this popular view of women was not a monolith, with many women refusing to leave their jobs once their husbands came back from the warfront; there was a distinct contrast between women and family life on television and on the streets. However, it is undeniable that the media portrayal of women after the war created a caricature that still remains in the minds of millions of Americans today (Oren, 2003). In a still-standing country after the dust of the Second World War began to settle, television was a means of projecting a return to normalcy in the form of the picturesque suburban life. It is for this reason that the popular shows of the time are worth analyzing in attempts to uncover how they reflected the state of mind of post-war America. The notion was emphasized and highlighted to millions of viewers at home through popular media and advertising, especially the burgeoning industry of television, still in its infancy at the time. Aggressive advertising of the dutiful domestic housewife pervaded American media during this time, and though in recent years debate has been sparked about whether or not its image is an accurate representation of the era, statistical evidence such as female college enrollment and the decreasing of the average age at marriage suggests that the prioritization of motherhood and housework had indeed cemented itself as a national ideal (Halliwell, 2007).

Related to the gender roles of the postwar period is the dynamic of marriage itself and the concept of the nuclear family. The archetype of a family unit consisting of a breadwinner father, his wife, and their children was created in the post-war era, supported by a leveling off of divorce rates, lower marriage ages, and an increasing birth rate (Olito, 2019 as cited by McCumber, 2020). Though television often did not reflect real life (only about 60% of American families

actually conformed to the archetype), its pervasiveness throughout pop culture indicates a societal value or aspiration to some degree. The emphasis on this idyllic life is underscored by a common, nationwide desire for stability; after the tumultuous period of war where families were disrupted or even changed forever with the death of an enlisted father, the children who emerged from World War II grew up with a desire to create a perfect familial life for their children that they themselves might not have enjoyed due to global circumstances (McCumber, 2020).

Television's portrayal of families is worthy of analysis, especially the ways in which showrunners handled situations in which they could be disrupted, most notably divorce. The skyrocketing of divorce did not occur until the late 60s and early 70s, and therefore was not portrayed in the media until after that, but the topic is still relevant when discussing the ethics of the 1950s (Murray, personal communication, 2022).

Case Studies

The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet

The glamorization of post-war suburban life is epitomized by the long-running sitcom *The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet*, featuring the real-life family composed of the Nelsons: parents Ozzie and Harriet along with their two sons David and Ricky. The show displayed a standard of what the quintessential American family should look like, which contributed to its self-proclaimed honor of being "America's favorite family". The show's premise took a slice-of-life approach, depicting the Nelsons' family dynamic as they navigate mundane activities such as schoolwork, growing pains, rivalries, and more (Weisblat in Newcomb, 1997). Episodes were generally lighthearted and unserious, with low stakes yet amicable characters that kept viewers tuned in. The show in general can be viewed as very safe; the chosen episodes of interest did not subvert societal norms at the time, but rather reinforced them. The picturesque

domestic lives of Ozzie and Harriet and later on David and Ricky and their respective wives especially showcase the era's expectations of the life's timeline.

For example, the season 13 episode "Kris's Girlfriend" centers on Ricky and his wife Kris as they struggle to adjust the rhythm of their married life when the latter's friend temporarily lives with them while moving (Grant et al., 1965). All three are still in college, implying that they are no older than their early twenties, yet Ricky and Kris are married, homeowners, and Ricky even has a job at a law firm. The accomplishment of these three at such early ages in their lifetime displays a much more accelerated life timeline than what is now considered normal in the 21st century. In 1960, a majority of men's first marriages occurred between the ages of 20 and 24, while those of women occurred between 18 and 24 (Hemez, 2020). It is notable that Kris is still enrolled in college after marrying Ricky, since women enrollment was rare at the time, but the episode is standard, hardly going out of its way to address any pervasive societal issues.

Other episodes such as "ESP" (focusing on a friendly rivalry between Ozzie and Harriet over which gender has better extrasensory perception) and "Wally's Pen Pal" (a Ricky-centered episode harking back to *Cyrano de Bergerac* and *Singin' In The Rain*) feature antics and hijinks for the fun of it, not attempting to make a grand statement or push the envelope (Grant et al., 1961, 1963). Because of its generally pleasant and safe plotlines, it comes as no surprise as to why the show was beloved by many throughout the nation and why it ran for so long. Put candidly, "The Nelsons [humorously] embodied wholesome, 'normal' American existence so conscientiously (if blandly) that their name epitomized upright, happy family life for decades" (Weisblat in Newcomb, 1997.). *The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet* therefore further

established the boundary of what was normal in society and on television, setting a baseline for other shows to push it instead, subverting it with humor.

I Love Lucy

I Love Lucy has earned its place in history as an iconic form of media; the familiar faces of Lucille Ball and Desi Arnaz (plus their plucky neighbors played by Vivian Vance and William Frawley) graced the screens of millions of viewers at home for over a decade and cemented their statuses as television greats through their weekly comedic antics. In general, the three episodes I viewed were exemplary of the common housewife/working husband dynamic that is often associated with the decade. One of the most iconic episodes of the show is “Job Switching”, a self-contained adventure in which Lucy, Ethel (Vance), Ricky (Arnaz), and Fred (Frawley) switch roles for a week, with the men taking up housework and the women earning money via formal employment in a chocolate factory (Oppenheimer et al., 1952). Watching the episode with a 21st century perspective, it is hard to determine whether or not it is satire of gender roles or reinforcement. Television in its infancy was almost always episodic in nature, where the status quo is always maintained and no significant changes persist over time. It could be interpreted that the hijinks that occur when Lucy and Ethel struggle to keep up on the assembly line or Ricky’s failure at making dinner (Figure 2) is an acknowledgement of how gender was divided, a way of saying “it’s not easy on the other side”. The episode even ends with the ladies and men acknowledging the struggles that the other gender faces in their “sphere” and agreeing to stay within their own. The show seems to tread a fine line between calling out the deeply entrenched gender roles of the time and reinforcing it by playing it for laughs. The true intentions of the writers and the show as a whole may be vague, but because the status quo remains by the episode’s end, it seems more likely that the episode pushes a newfound appreciation for men and

women’s “separate spheres”, with the caveat that this does not necessarily mean that they should start bleeding into one another (Murray, personal communication, 2022).

Figure 2

Lucy and Ethel struggle in the workplace (left) while Ricky and Fred struggle in the kitchen (right).

Note. Asher, W., (1952).

The common views of marriage dynamics were also on full display; the show showed both ends of the spectrum through the two central couples. Though Lucy and Ricky are frequently at odds, there is a mutual love and respect for each other at its core. On the other hand, Ethel and Fred more often than not show disdain and general annoyance with each other, though the audience is expected to understand that they too share the same love deep down that their neighbors share, albeit underneath layers of jokes at the others’ expense. The primary dynamic comedy between Ethel and Fred stems from the “ball and chain” joke that implies imprisonment in marriage; the joke has its roots in American vaudeville, a type of theatrical entertainment popular from the late 19th century to the early 20th century (Murray, personal communication, 2022; White, 2016).

This type of humor was not the only way that vaudeville influenced the show. Ball draws clear inspirations from the artform in her portrayal of Lucy Ricardo, using her trademark physical comedy to not only invoke gender stereotypes in episodes, but subvert them as well (White, 2016). Lucy enjoys herself as a homemaker, but many episodes see her itching to break out of it, such as “Lucy Does A TV Commercial” (colloquially known as the “Vitameatavegemin” episode), where she agrees to do a commercial for a supplement that is mostly pure alcohol, but gets drunker with each subsequent take; another example is “Lucy’s Italian Movie”, where she is eager to research for a role she landed while on vacation in Europe, but finds herself in the deep end (Oppenheimer et al., 1952; 1956). Ball’s slapstick comedy present in landmark episodes like those aforementioned often paints her character to look foolish and unladylike, but Lucy’s spunk and charisma is what endeared her to millions across the country, subverting the societal expectations that women should always be prim and proper (White, 2016). The show managed to entertain audiences all while subconsciously challenging the norms of the time, a true feat for one of the first sitcoms to pioneer the medium.

The Danny Thomas Show

The Danny Thomas Show (originally titled *Make Room For Daddy* for its first three seasons) exhibits interesting examples when it comes to portraying gender roles and the nuclear family. The show’s early premise revolved around Thomas’s character Danny Williams and his relationship with his wife and children while juggling a career as a successful nightclub entertainer. The three episodes chosen for analysis all came after the show’s channel move from ABC to CBS, which carried along with it several changes in production. Not only was the show’s title changed to the more generic *The Danny Thomas Show*, but Jean Hagen—who played Thomas’s wife Margaret—had left shortly after filming the third season for several reasons,

namely a desire to pursue film and theatre (Liebman in Newcomb, 1997). Thomas and producer Sheldon Leonard were now faced with the difficult task of explaining Hagen's departure. Due to the existing views of divorce at the time, it would have been absolutely unacceptable to have the couple split up, so the decision was made to kill off the character instead, establishing Danny as a widower. The show's fourth season saw him going on dates with several guest stars and a dip in ratings proved that the viewers were not interested in a Williams family that was incomplete. By the season's end, Danny became engaged to Kathy (played by Marjorie Lord), introduced as a nurse when his son Rusty falls ill with the measles. The fact that divorce was a nonstarter as a reason to explain something as unserious as the departure of a television character speaks volumes about its status as a societal taboo. It was to the point where death was actually viewed as less shameful than acknowledgement that marriage was not working, the underlying reason being that death meant an *involuntary* end to marriage—the fault being placed on God, life, or the forces of the universe—rather than a *voluntary* decision by the parties involved, which inherently implies shortcomings and mistakes by one or both parties. The departure of Hagen and the introduction of Kathy alone speak volumes about the effects that societal values have on art, though individual episodes also act as valiant efforts to make statements on these same expectations.

The most prominent portrayal and commentary of these domestic values come in the season four episode "Uncle Tonoose Pays A Visit", where Danny's Lebanese uncle (Thomas's real-life ethnicity) visits him with the intention of finding him a wife (Stander, 1957). The premise alone exemplifies the 50s idea of the nuclear family being the standard of life; up until this point, many had been hounding Danny about how long it has taken him to remarry. Though the show temporarily explores the idea of single parenthood, an interesting deviation from the

norm, the focused emphasis on completing his family reinforces societal expectations of the time. Tonoose's "old world" views and ideas of marriage are played for laughs as he constantly stresses that what makes a good woman and wife is her ability to do housework and keep quiet; his antics can be summed up his attempts to marry off a (mostly silent) woman named Sharifa to Danny despite the fact that he already is in the middle of a date. Tonoose represents the misogynistic archetype of relegating women to little more than docile domestic servants to their husbands. The interesting aspect of the episode, however, is its climax, wherein Danny gives an impassioned speech addressing Uncle Tonoose's viewpoints, stressing how women should be treated as people rather than objects. He highlights the fact that Tonoose had never taken Sharifa's thoughts into account, thinking about whether or not she even wants to marry rather than chasing another life pursuit. The scene is a rare moment of self-awareness of the current societal environment. The episode ends with Tonoose taking the lesson to heart, but resetting the status quo by silencing Sharifa as she was about to speak, playing it for laughs. The immediate regression back to old habits is an age-old trope, but it should not be taken as a loss altogether, as if nothing was achieved. The episode accomplishes the task of opening up the audience by employing humor; once their guard is down, they can be hit with the truth.

The Dick Van Dyke Show

These portrayals of domestic life start to shift as the 50s come and go and television enters the 1960s; juxtaposing the dynamic of television couples in programs such as *I Love Lucy* with that of *The Dick Van Dyke Show* presents an interesting difference. Though there are still the occasional jokes that poke fun at the perceived inferiority of women (e.g. one line in "All About Eavesdropping" is "I hope they never send a woman to space"), the humor reliant on hating one's spouse is almost completely absent. In addition, in *I Love Lucy* and even *The Danny*

Thomas Show, women were often pitted against the men in plots (i.e. Lucy is always at odds with Ricky, Ethel with Fred, or Kathy with Danny); there is a sense of cooperation and collaboration between Laura and Rob Petrie that was somewhat refreshing to see. The conflicts were rarely between the couple (i.e. Rob vs. Laura), but more often against them (i.e. Rob and Laura vs. the problem).

The season three episode “All About Eavesdropping” is exemplary of this; it sees the Petries preparing to spend an evening with their neighbors when they accidentally listen in on their private conversation that happens to be quite negative about them. The rest of the plot is a tense and cringeful yet humorous situation as their neighbors wonder why their best friends are suddenly giving them the cold shoulder (Keller & Merrill, 1963). In addition, “Never Bathe On Saturday” sees Laura get her toe stuck in a bathtub faucet (Figure 3) while on vacation and Rob’s attempts to enter the locked bathroom with minimal collateral damage (Reiner, 1965). The episode could have presented an easy opportunity for Laura and Rob to get at each other’s throats, as well as to present her as an idiot (she is called one, but by a maid that she unknowingly insulted, not Rob). However, the show chooses to pursue other means of conflict, by portraying Rob as crazy as well (having been caught painting on a mustache and talking to himself in an accent in anticipation for roleplay with his wife) and the main antagonists being the hotel staff inadvertently hindering his attempts to help her (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Rob Petrie paints himself a mustache (left) while Laura Petrie makes a big mistake (right).

Note. Paris, J., (1965).

Though the media has attempted to normalize and standardize the ideas of a perfect family and married life, television treaded the line between reinforcing it and subverting the trope, paving the way for the evolution of marriage and family dynamics in the future. Some of the most iconic episodes in the runs of *I Love Lucy*, *The Danny Thomas Show*, and more achieve a precarious balance of humor and hard truth, contributing to a slow evolution that would ultimately loosen up these societal expectations, both in television but the real world as well as audiences were subconsciously influenced; later shows would continue the cycle as the American family progressed alongside history.

The 60s-70s: Cold War Apex and Counter-Culture

Historical Context

Following the fallout of World War II, most of Europe and parts of the Pacific were in shambles. As the dust settled, only two superpowers remained: the United States and the Soviet Union (USSR). The two fought on the same side as part of the Allies yet on different fronts, but these relations began to fall apart as early as the Potsdam Conference just months after the war ended (John F. Kennedy Library, n.d.). The big debate that now loomed over the world was over

which ideology was best for governing, now that the borders had reset and unrest began to foment in colonial territories. The United States had long established its self-appointed role as the defender of democracy via capitalism and aligned itself as the foe against communism and authoritarian regimes, the most threatening being that of the USSR. For the next five decades, the world would enter a new era marked by tension as the new global superpowers were locked in a staring contest, nuclear war looming in the background. While the U.S. and Soviet Union never directly fought, other nations were used as pawns in the grand chess game of political ideology. A number of proxy wars were fought during the five decades of conflict where both superpowers provided support of various kinds (e.g. financial, political, and military) to governments who supported their philosophy (Council on Foreign Relations, n.d.) The Soviet Union backed countries that promoted communism, wherein the government controls the economy and other aspects of life, while the United States supported countries who operated on the more democratic capitalism, a system where the economy is controlled by the free market which theoretically allows for more personal freedom.

Though the Cold War technically began in the late 40s, its presence in mainstream television was less pronounced during the 50s, which explains its absence in the previous section. However, as the “war” dragged on through the 60s, the cracks began to show in the United States. Political unrest began to ferment and manifest in various ways as Americans began to question their “fundamental assumptions about the role of the [US] government in domestic and world affairs” (Tovares in Newcomb, 1997.). Certain television programs took the opportunity to dramatize and satirize the aforementioned proxy wars, often commentating on them. In addition, espionage became a common motif throughout the Cold War, with both the US and the USSR engaging in intelligence missions in order to obtain valuable information on the

enemy's military and technological progress (Llewellyn & Thompson, 2020). These internal changes that occurred simultaneously in response to those of the global geopolitical climate also manifested as a counterculture that formed in the 1960s. The term "counterculture" denotatively means a movement that rejects, opposes, and rebels against the current culture in place (British Library, 2006, as cited by McEachern, 2017). However, in the context of US history it has come to represent the broader phenomenon of the various overlapping movements that comprised it; for its expression through stand-out television of the era, a few themes are especially of interest: the anti-war movement, its associated hippie culture, and second-wave feminism.

Case Studies

Get Smart

Get Smart was very much a product of the resurging popularity of spy fiction during the apex of the Cold War. Though the genre had its roots in the nineteenth century, authors were drawn back to the world of government and intelligence every time a major world conflict arose; for example, as fascism spread throughout Germany, Italy, and Spain, the looming Second World War presented an interesting global climate that writers found inspiration in. As WWII transitioned into the Cold War, the United States and the Soviet Union became the new pawns of the genre; the chess game between the American CIA and the Soviet KGB and its surrounding mystery left much to be desired and fulfilled by novelists, though little of the spies' work on the page was actually occurring in the real world (Polmar, 1997). The show centers around the American intelligence agency CONTROL battling against KAOS, the international organization of evil. Maxwell Smart and the unnamed Agent 99 served as the show's protagonists, frequently coming toe-to-toe with various KAOS agents ranging in ability and rank in the organization. KAOS was vaguely European—a nod to the actual opponent in historical context—though most

often agents were German. Though puzzling at first for a show produced during the zeitgeist of American/Soviet conflict, German spies were not exactly out of the norm. As a result of the Potsdam conference at the end of WWII, Germany was demilitarized and divided into four sections, each to be occupied by one of the Allied powers. As its capital, Berlin received the same treatment; the city would then be considered the capital of the Cold War due to the sheer amount of spies from America, Britain, Germany, France, and Russia present at any given point (Polmar, 1997). Because of its joint occupancy by several countries, the city eventually became a hub for government espionage.

None of the episodes chosen for analysis demonstrated heavy commentary on the state of the Cold War; however the premise of the show and the general structure of episodes presents a much more subliminal message regarding the metaphorical chess game between the two world powers. The show's generalization as a parody of spy fiction says much about the agenda (or lack thereof) that it pushes. Purely for entertainment and capitalizing off of the success of the genre, the show hardly took itself seriously and chewed the scenery that was so often bugged or rigged with various spy gadgets. Max and CONTROL almost always win in their spats against KAOS, and in the rare instances that they do not, the status quo resets by the next episode's start. The season 2 episode "A Spy for a Spy" is most exemplary of this, wherein the Chief of CONTROL is kidnapped by KAOS executive Siegfried, and Smart retaliates by kidnapping their top assassin for leverage. A war of abduction begins, climaxing to the point where Max and Siegfried are the only ones left untouched. The episode ends with two buses in a parking lot as the two organizations swap out each of their agents one by one, leveling the playing field for future escapades (Marmer & Burns, 1966).

CONTROL's enduring triumph (or at the very least, stalemate) against KAOS implies a "benefit of the doubt" interpretation of the exact standings at this point in the Cold War. It is quite the juxtaposition given the growing apprehension in the public as a result of protests against the Vietnam War, the crux of the civil rights movement, and more; Americans were slowly starting to question their trust in the government and its role in international affairs (Tovares in Newcomb, 1997). At times, the show—thinly veiled by the novelty of bizarre spy gadgets—was able to sneak in some subversive statements about political issues in a humorous, and therefore non-threatening way. As one of the most popular shows of its time, the escapades of Smart, Agent 99, and CONTROL characterized a hyper fictionalized world of thrill and tension. Its extremely subtle way of questioning the government's position in the geopolitical climate set the stage for more biting commentary in the following decade as the tension began to bubble over.

M*A*S*H

One of the most obvious allegories of the geopolitical climate demonstrated via the sitcom is *M*A*S*H* (short for Mobile Army Surgical Hospital), its premise revolving around the 4077th surgical unit and its key personnel. Though the series is set during the Korean War (which lasted from 1950-1953), its run from 1972 to 1983 slightly overlapped with the Vietnam War (1955-1975), a proxy war that would prove to be paramount to domestic attitudes towards America's fight for democracy due to its status as the first televised war (and therefore the first war wherein Americans would see news footage of men dying at the front lines) (Council on Foreign Relations, n.d.; Spector, 2016). When asked if *M*A*S*H* was about Korea or Vietnam, showrunner Larry Gelbart stated that it was about both, specifying that although it took place in Korea during its war the contemporary events of Vietnam are what give the show its meaning,

something that is often lost on viewers (Denny, 1986). The premise of the show alone is enough to portray how television was influenced by its societal context, but individual episodes further demonstrate its response, commentating on the then-ongoing Vietnam War (using the now-finished Korean War) with little pushback from the network on the extent to which they would criticize the government and support in terms of commentary on the wastefulness of war (Denny, 1986). Many of the show's most beloved episodes came out on top due to how subversive they were during their time, pushing the envelope of what could be done on television.

The season one episode "Sometimes You Hear The Bullet" is an excellent example of how the show used comedy to open the audience's eyes to the often-overlooked horrors of war. The episode centers around an injured Marine at the 4077th itching to recover to see combat again, with chief surgeon Benjamin "Hawkeye" Pierce (Alan Alda) discovering that the young man—only 15 years old—used his older brother's ID to enlist and serve in the war. Later on in the episode Hawkeye fails to save an old friend shot by enemy fire on the front lines, resulting in the show's first instance in which a patient is not saved and a main character is visibly shaken by the loss (Figure 4). Not wanting to see another young man die in combat, Hawkeye reports the underage Marine and has him sent home, at peace with the knowledge that although the young man may hate him for the rest of his life, at least it will be "a long healthy hate" (Kleinschmitt, 1973). Through the young marine and Hawkeye, the show juxtaposes two differing viewpoints at two differing stages of experience: the former's optimistic and patriotic eagerness to fight for his country and the latter's disillusioned apathy towards the war as a result of watching so many young men die. Hawkeye's success at preventing one more premature death ultimately sends the message that what he did was the right thing to do. It shines a spotlight on the senseless killing

that went unspoken during the real Korean War, but with the then-current Vietnam War, the message remained ever so relevant. The episode proved to be an early realization of potential for the series, marking a first step towards its classification as a dramedy blending both drama and comedy (Denny, 1986).

Figure 4

Hawkeye (left) cries for the first time after failing to save his dying friend.

Note. Gelbart, L., (1975).

It is through Hawkeye that the anti-war message manifests the most clearly, with his sarcastic attitude towards the war and his role in it being a key part of his personality. Much of it can be attributed to Alda himself, who was apprehensive about the series at first due to an unwillingness for the war to be “a backdrop for lighthearted hijinks at the front”, wanting to show its horrors instead through the more palatable medium of comedy (Denny, 1986). In the earlier more humorous season one episode “Tuttle”, he constructs the identity of a fake soldier in order to cover up his diversion of camp supplies to a nearby orphanage; the lie snowballs as he ropes in Radar (the 4077’s clerk) and Trapper (a fellow doctor) to assist in proving his existence, culminating in Captain Tuttle’s “death” and his G.I. insurance (plus fourteen months of backpay)

being given to the orphanage (Shelly & Ketchum, 1973). His chaotic acts of good in the episode contrast with the good that he does on the front line, the show seemingly making the argument that supplies and money going to an orphanage is much more useful than what it would contribute to a war that the country has a questionable role in.

“Sometimes You Hear The Bullet” was only the beginning for the show’s dissemination of an anti-war message; the series crossed another important threshold with the season three finale “Abyssinia, Henry”, named as one of the top episodes of television of all time at the turn of the century (*TV Guide*, 1997). The ending comes as a dramatic shock to viewers, who up until this point were entertained by the 4077’s commanding officer Henry Blake’s (McLean Stevenson) honorable discharge and preparations to return home. The episode overall is lighthearted, with much of the time dedicated to Blake’s paternal relationship with Radar and a going-away party thrown by Hawkeye and the others. It is only at the end after his departure that his fate is revealed by Radar: his plane shot down by enemy fire over the Sea of Japan with no survivors (Greenbaum & Fritzell, 1975). *M*A*S*H* historian James Wittebols (2003) notes that it marked a first in television wherein "a major character leaving a series dies in a tragic way", though as established with *The Danny Thomas Show*, this is not necessarily true; as aforementioned, Margaret Williams was killed off following the show's network jump when Jean Hagen declined to return during its hiatus. To nitpick, it comes down to semantics. The defining difference between the two was that Hagen's departure was unplanned and therefore dismissed with a casual mention and a handwave when the show returned without her. In fact, the first episode that aired on CBS made no mention of Margaret's absence; Danny even continued to wear his wedding ring even when proposing to Kathy despite being single for the entire season. Margaret received no grand send-off that Blake was given on his show, which makes the impact

of the news of his death resonate louder with audiences. Wittebols is correct in the sense that "Abyssinia, Henry" is the first episode on television in which a main character's death is a deliberate plot point with momentum leading up to the reveal, but it is not the first time that a main cast member's departure was handled in such a way. Margaret Williams simply disappeared from her series (almost as if she never existed), but Henry Blake had truly died. All in all, it is still undeniable that Blake's death was as shocking as it was unconventional.

Since Stevenson's departure from the show was planned ahead of time, producers Gene Reynolds and Larry Gelbart took the opportunity to make a louder statement about the horrors of war, especially with the Vietnam War salient in viewers' minds. The concept of abrupt death is not new to the series, with the aforementioned episode "Sometimes You Hear The Bullet" doing the same to a close friend of Hawkeye's. However, "Abyssinia, Henry" is much more significant because of the same treatment given to a beloved main character that viewers intimately know; the largely humorous episode disarms the audience, opening their minds to its unpleasant realities. Reynolds explained his intent behind the decision to kill off Blake, drawing on the idea that the grief is hardly felt when strangers on television (both real and fictional) die: "It was a surprise, it was somebody they loved. They didn't expect it but it made the point. People like Henry Blake are lost in war" (Denny, 1986). These episodes are exemplary of a larger push towards tragicomedy after Blake's death as the show continued to comment on America's role in defending democracy through militaristic means.

Aside from the obvious allegories to the Vietnam War and the other proxy wars of the era, *M*A*S*H* also demonstrated a shift in societal views in other ways, namely the evolution of sexuality. The taboo of sexuality will be discussed further in the analysis of *The Addams Family*, but holistically, the show does not shy away from the loosening restrictions on its portrayal.

Much of the humor stems from the promiscuity of the characters, many of them in affairs (e.g. Margaret Houlihan and Frank Burns) or sleeping with a new partner every episode (e.g. Hawkeye), showing a hard left turn from the conservative side-stepping of television in the 50s. The show's huge popularity cemented its place in television and American history, largely in part to its layered commentary on military intervention as a byproduct of the larger Cold War. It did refrain from critiques of warmaking from a macro perspective, but its character-driven structure was more than effective in portraying the wastefulness of war from the perspectives of individuals trying to cope in an environment thrust upon them.

The Addams Family

The eponymous Addams family is worthy of plenty of analysis in terms of the work the show did in parodying and subverting the idea of what the perfect American family should look like, but its broader, odder lifestyle is of special concern in this thesis. Its largest contribution to the pop culture of the midcentury is that the show—along with similar ones of the era that centered on supernatural beings such as *The Munsters*, *Charmed*, and *I Dream of Jeannie*—is that their statuses as “fish out of water” highlighted their refusal to conform to society, therefore “align[ing] them with the burgeoning counterculture” (Cox, as cited by Morowitz, 2007). The Addamses represented the hippie culture that was beginning to blossom in the mid-60s through physical traits such as Morticia's (and Cousin Itt's) long hair, their quasi-Victorian clothing, and general eccentricities (Morowitz, 2007). The bohemian lifestyle that characterized its earlier stages is especially emphasized, with creative pursuits on full display such as Lurch's musical talents and Morticia's artistry as well as the Victorian atmosphere of the home. The show also touches on the more iconic elements of the burgeoning youth culture, such as the emergence of rock and teenage heartthrobs (Morowitz, 2007). “Lurch The Teenage Idol” sees the titular family

butler—an imposing figure standing at 6’9” with a booming baritone—become a national icon after recording radio hits, with teenagers almost throwing themselves at him (Henning et al., 1965). The episode is evocative of the meteoric rise to stardom and the fan culture surrounding it, such as those of Elvis Presley or The Beatles.

One of the more prominent displays of the emerging alternative lifestyle is embedded in the relationship between Gomez (John Astin) and Morticia (Carolyn Jones); the show never shied away from the erotic passion between the couple (actually becoming a running gag), reflecting the changing views on sexuality at the time. This also broke the taboo around marital sex that had been pervasive on television, which was manifested in shows such as *I Love Lucy* and *The Dick Van Dyke Show* that depicted married couples sleeping in separate beds with difficult means for intimacy. As Astin explained in an interview, his and Jones’s characters were the first married couple on television “who seem to actually have a sex life”, proposing that their romance be sensual and “unceasing” (Cox, as cited by Morowitz, 2007). The greatest example of this was the running joke in which any invocation of the French language—from “*c’est merveilleux*” to “ensemble”—by Morticia would lead to Gomez drowning her with kisses (Figure 5). This infatuation and their marriage’s origins are revealed via a two-parter in the show’s second season titled “Morticia’s Romance”, both being the show’s highest rated on IMDb. Not only does the episode show Morticia and Gomez’s passion at its most palpable as the two slowly fall in love, but the former’s macabre eccentricities are treated as preferable (and even normal) compared to those of her twin sister Ophelia, who is excessively perky with a hint of chaos (Winkler & Coons, 1965). The show holistically portrayed counterculture in a flattering light, celebrating its protagonists’ quirks, presenting the comforting idea that “the different” could also be lovable, and that imperfections in life are not all that strange (Morowitz, 2007).

This crossing of invisible lines was allowed due to the established nonconforming nature of the family, and therefore allowed an avenue to push its boundaries. Its celebration as protagonists despite their nonconforming idiosyncrasies therefore portray alternative lifestyles in a more palatable way for audiences, no matter their degree of liberal attitudes.

Figure 5

Gomez (left) fervently kisses Morticia (right) with each invocation of French.

Note. Lanfield, S., (1965).

All In The Family

For the same reasons as other television shows included in this study, *All In The Family* cemented its status as one of the United States' greatest series in history, garnering accolades from publications such as *TV Guide*, *TIME Magazine*, and the Writers Guild of America. Centering on the Bunkers (patriarch Archie, his loving wife Edith, their feminist daughter Gloria, and her beatnik husband Mike), a working-class family in Queens, New York, the show chronicles its members' daily lives, often using comedy to bring important issues to light, from homosexuality to the Vietnam War. The season two episode "Edith's Problem" is exemplary of the show's willingness to speak openly about certain taboo topics in a standard episode, in this

case menopause. The normally loving Edith suddenly has wild mood swings, throwing the family off guard; Gloria realizes that her mother is beginning menopause, and urges Archie to be considerate during this period of change (Zacharias & Styler, 1972). Menopause remains as much of a taboo today as it did in the mid 1970s, stemming from a general belief that its hormonal changes bring a sense of change that is usually negative (Berry, 2022). Edith's worries hold up to this, as she spends much of the episode worrying about becoming a decrepit senior and not being attractive to Archie. Through Jean Stapleton's comedic performance as Edith, the episode brings the issue to the forefront, not only normalizing it through its portrayal on television, but assuring Edith (and by extension, the viewers at home) that there is nothing to be concerned about.

Widely regarded as one of the show's best episodes, "Sammy's Visit" deconstructs the character of Archie Bunker using the popular trope of a celebrity cameo, musician Sammy Davis Jr. in this case (Dana, 1972). The plot centers around Davis's visit to the Bunker household in an attempt to retrieve a forgotten briefcase before heading to the airport, Archie having been his cab driver. Sammy is held hostage as he waits in the house for the cab company to deliver his briefcase, with Archie's attempts at small talk only worsening the situation, rattling off "one outrageously bigoted notion after another" (Garner, 2002). As showrunner Norman Lear explained, the episode had a recipe for comedic perfection: "Archie Bunker and a black man. Archie Bunker and a black man who happens to be a celebrity. Archie Bunker and a black man who's a celebrity and has a glass eye. And he's Jewish. You know, it was amazing" (Garner, 2002). The episode climaxes as the briefcase finally arrives, and Sammy insists on getting a picture with his new friend. As the shutter closes, he plants a kiss on Archie's cheek (Figure 6), the latter's smile slowly dissipating into shock and horror; the scene garnered such an uproarious

reaction from the audience that it produced the show’s longest sustained laughter, often being edited down for syndication (Garner, 2002). The show often subtly makes the statement that Archie is not a character one might like to emulate, his bigotry often the target of ridicule from others; regardless, the characters hardly do much to change him. However, this episode takes it to the extreme, with Archie’s innocently insensitive and racist comments coming back to bite him, embarrassing himself in front of Sammy and coming to a head in a laser-guided karmic fashion. The episode is a perfect example of Lear’s attempts to humorize the conservative and prejudiced attitudes of the family’s patriarch, with CBS even going as far to preemptively showing a disclaimer reading that the show “seeks to throw a humorous spotlight on our frailties, prejudices and concerns. By making them a source of laughter, [the show hopes] to show—in a mature fashion—just how absurd they are” (Garner, 2002).

Figure 6

Sammy Davis Jr. kisses Archie Bunker on the cheek, much to the latter’s horror.

Note. Rich, J., (1972).

One of the show’s most heavy-handed examples of commentary comes in the form of the season seven episode, “The Draft Dodger”, wherein the Bunkers have Christmas dinner with Archie’s friend Pinky—whose son died in the Vietnam War—and Mike’s old mate David, who

evaded the draft by fleeing to Canada (Moriarty & Milligan, 1976). The slapstick humor of Archie repeatedly being soaked by a gag gift meant for Pinky is underpinned by tension as a result of dramatic irony; everyone in the household aside from them knows of David's true reasons for residing up north. The plot finally climaxes when the patriotic Archie grills David about his reasons for living in Canada, leading to his revealing of the truth that he is a draft dodger. Archie explodes, only further agitated when Edith, Gloria, and especially Mike defend David (Mike's impassioned line "When will you admit that the war was wrong?" is particularly incendiary); he calls on Pinky to voice his opinion, thinking he will be supported, but his tone is surprisingly quite the opposite. Pinky is much more conciliatory, saying that his son also hated the war, but both men did what they felt they had to do; he extends a handshake of forgiveness towards David, acknowledging that his son would have done the same (Figure 7); this moment in particular garnered strong applause from the live audience. Archie is stunned but respects the decision, admitting that he needs time to fully process the night's events. The show takes a hard stance on the morality of the Vietnam War, leaning in the same direction as *M*A*S*H*; in the wake of the withdrawal of the last American troops from Vietnam, the country was still in a state of wondering about the point of U.S. involvement at the expense of thousands of lives. Pinky's act of forgiveness towards David (and Archie's acceptance of it) represents a reconciliation of two camps and sends the message that a middle ground can be found in the midst of the polarizing divisions spurred by the war. Though the core of Archie's character is his bigotry, his capability for change and willingness to evolve his ideals at the end of the episode acts as a sort of model for Americans to follow as well. Through lovable characters, gripping plotlines, and biting humor, *All In The Family* was a landmark sitcom that changed the way that audiences watched television.

Figure 7

Pinky extends a handshake of reconciliation to David.

Note. Bogart, P., (1976).

The Mary Tyler Moore Show

Going from being a main character on her TV husband's show to headlining her own, Mary Tyler Moore's evolution from devoted wife Laura Petrie on *The Dick Van Dyke Show* to working woman Mary Richards on her eponymous series coincided with another offshoot of the 1970s counter-culture, second wave feminism. While the first wave of feminism occurred in the early 20th century as a movement that centered around the right of women's suffrage, the succeeding wave picked up steam in the midst of counterculture of the 1960s and 70s, focusing now on all other aspects of the female experience: gender equality at work, in politics, family, and especially sexuality (Burkett, 1998.). *The Mary Tyler Moore Show* was significant in the sense that its protagonist was a working woman in her 30s whose life did not revolve around finding a man, though she never shied away from the possibility of finding love when it arose. What distinguished her from other single TV women at the time was the fact that the latter were

usually widowed or divorced, still seeking a husband to support them; though Mary occasionally dated around on the show, it did not define her character and was not her top priority, evident by the fact that she was still single when the show ended in 1977. In turn, the success of the series set a new standard for what would come to be known as the “working woman” subgenre of the sitcom, wherein a woman’s aspirations and desires were centered around her career, not her marital status. The chosen episodes of analysis did not yield any particularly biting commentaries of societal norms at the time, but a few general themes were present. For example, the evolving ideas on sexuality as aforementioned took on a different form in the show, as it normalized premarital sex through the characters’ personal lives. It is treated as completely normal for both men and women to sleep around, and sexual double entendres were frequent.

However, there is a particular episode that stands out for a different reason; the season seven episode “Chuckles Bites The Dust” is regarded as one of the show’s best, not for any specific societal commentary, but for more of an existential one. Chuckles the Clown, a rarely-seen TV personality working at WJM-TV (the show’s workplace setting), dies offscreen in a freak accident after being mauled by an elephant during a parade. Leading up to the funeral, the staff constantly make jokes about the bizarre circumstances of his death, much to Mary’s annoyance; she scolds everyone for their disrespect, but her coworkers fail to keep a straight face. Finally at the funeral, everyone is reverent and properly mourning, but it is now Mary who cannot pull herself together as she stifles laughter with each additional word from the priest. When it seems that she is about to be chided for her inappropriate behavior, he applauds her bravery for laughing and encourages her to continue; in true comedic fashion, Mary instead breaks down in sobs (Lloyd, 1975). Hilarious, absurd, and a bit dark, the episode speaks to the human condition as more of a meta commentary on the purpose of humor and comedy in life,

offering a valuable coping mechanism in times of strife. As Lou Grant (the boss at WJM-TV, played by Ed Asner) tells her in the episode, “It’s a release. A kind of defense mechanism. It’s like whistling in a graveyard. You laugh at something that scares you. We laugh at death because we know death will have the last laugh on us” (Lloyd, 1975). Lou’s wise words are seen in action as everyone who cracks jokes at Chuckles’s expense are seen as having processed their grief in a way that allows them to be properly respectful at the funeral; as callous and ridiculous as it may be, it was an important step in their grieving process. Because Mary denies herself of this out of respect for the dead, she deprives herself of a proper grieving process, resulting in the rollercoaster of emotions that she speedruns within minutes on the day of the funeral. Tragedy is not limited to a certain era, as everyday we find ourselves caught in a new struggle. However, in the context of such a tumultuous time period (from the recent Vietnam War to domestic political upheaval), perhaps the message of Chuckles’s unfortunate demise resonated a bit louder. This theme of using humor to cope with devastation is evergreen; it arises again at the turn of the 21st century as America comes to terms with one of its biggest tragedies.

Despite not making any particularly loud statements through its episodes, the premise of *The Mary Tyler Moore Show* as a whole serves as commentary on changing values for women at the time, as it normalized the idea of a working woman whose top priority was not settling down. The show defied gender expectations of the previous decade, pushing an agenda that celebrated women who based their success in life on other measures besides marital status, without putting down those that did. It signaled to women across America that career aspirations are just as important to one’s womanhood than domestic ones, opening their world to more possibilities (Chaney, 2017). Though it did not radically transform the medium overnight, it made valuable progress by making room for other working female protagonists; future TV women like Murphy

Brown, Ally McBeal, Liz Lemon (*30 Rock*) and Leslie Knope (*Parks and Recreation*) owe a debt of gratitude to Mary Richards.

The 80s-90s: Cold War End and the “Triumph” of Capitalism

Historical Context

Though the world was still in the midst of the Cold War upon leaving the 70s and entering the 80s, there were signs that things were beginning to warm up. The tumult of the Vietnam War had overshadowed the beginnings of the period of *détente*, an ease of tensions between the U.S. and the U.S.S.R; there was an overall softening of relations that was occurring between the east and the west, a very welcome change after the stress of earlier events such as the Cuban Missile Crisis (the closest the world has gotten to nuclear war). Another manifestation of *détente*, the Helsinki Accords signed in the mid 70s was the product of negotiations between America and the Soviet Union, one of the points dealing with increasing trade with each other (Granata, 2022). This was only accelerated when Mikhail Gorbachev came to power in the Soviet Union in the mid 80s; inheriting an inefficient, collectivized country that was barely scraping by, he resigned to the harsh reality that the USSR could not keep up with the US (Granata, 2022). With subsequent national reforms operating on the policies of *glasnost* (openness) and *perestroika* (restructuring), Gorbachev opened the country to the rest of the world by slowly adopting western ideas. Perestroika in particular was significant; in restructuring the economy to accommodate a larger private sector, the USSR was essentially slowly giving into the argument that capitalism was indeed superior to communism. From the perspective of the rest of the world (and especially the United States), it seemed like in the longstanding struggle between capitalism and communism, the former was actually winning.

Consumerism saw another boom in the United States, partially spurred by the luxury style that President Ronald Reagan brought to the White House upon his inauguration (Gerhardt, n.d.). The booming economy resulted in a rise in disposable income, allowing Americans to spend more money on the widening range of goods or even luxuries as a way to show off their prosperity (Johnson & Baker, 2012). Economic affluence continued into the 90s as the United States entered a trade partnership with Mexico and Canada, cemented by the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), which allowed for the nation to continue its expansion into the global market (Gerhardt, n.d.).

Societal reflection of ideals became less targeted towards particular issues and broadened in scope; the global context that informed television therefore reflected a general air of opulence and affluence as a result of a belief that wealth was attainable for all Americans. The broadening of topics and loosening of focus reflects the state of television at the turn of the century; as choices began to multiply, audiences were no longer watching the same thing and the national culture began to fracture and branch out into more specific niches. The extent to which society actually resembled what was shown on the small screen is debatable, but the 1980s' portrayal of American wealth nevertheless was an allusion to the idea that the general public thought had prevailed at the time. There was also a general wholesomeness that pervaded television of the era; the gritty and biting satire of the 70s (exemplified by the aforementioned *M*A*S*H* and *All In The Family*) morphed into a more light-hearted and subliminal commentary. Even when topics got more serious, they were enveloped in warm humor that softened the blow, “the darker moments...couched in a kind of ABC After School Special lesson” (Gerhart, n.d.). This general lighthearted opulence is manifested in all of the shows of interest during the 80s and 90s and it is through the shows' premises that a reflection of society is seen, rather than their specific

commentary on topical issues; memorable episodes that made statements were still apparent, though broader issues were fair game.

Case Studies

The Golden Girls

From the first line of its iconic theme song, “Thank you for being a friend”, *The Golden Girls* established from the beginning its focus on found families through wholesome friendships. The ensemble cast centered on Dorothy (a divorcée), her widowed mother Sophia, and fellow widows Rose and Blanche, with episodes often about their efforts to live life to the fullest even in their golden years. In a similar way to *The Mary Tyler Moore Show*, *The Golden Girls* showcased how fulfilling life can still be when deviating from the normal life path; in both cases, the women’s lives found meaning outside of romantic relationships most of the time (through her career in the former and friendships for the latter). The opulence of the era is on full display, as it is never truly explained why the women live in such a nice house on the beachfront of Miami. All the women equally enjoy comfortable lifestyles, with the expectation that the audience would not question how the mortgage is being paid or what funds their comfortable retirements. The show was just one of many that contributed to the trend of TV families enjoying a life of affluence; it manifested in a larger reaction to the rising consumerism of the time along with the more symbolic winning of capitalism at the end of the Cold War (the fall of the Berlin Wall occurring halfway through the show’s run in 1989).

Keeping in line with the vibrancy of the protagonists, the show featured a deep seated wholesomeness that enveloped any topical issues that it chose to comment on. “Ladies of the Evening” offers an interesting evolution of views on sexuality that have so far been traced since the 1960s (Fanaro & Nathan, 1986). As a result of unfortunate circumstances and bad luck,

Blanche, Dorothy, and Rose's party plans are spoiled when the hotel they are staying at is raided by police due to its status as a prostitution hub. Despite their oblivion and protests, all three end up arrested when they are mistaken as prostitutes (Figure 8). The show as a whole already builds on the progress of the 1970s by portraying the active sex lives of its protagonists, Blanche especially; it was lauded for emphasizing female friendship and networks in a wholesome way (Nill in Newcomb, 1997). However, this episode in particular handles an offshoot of sexual liberation in a palatable manner, bringing the issue of sex work forward for gentle discussion. The protagonists represent the general society's views on sex work, Blanche being the most critical with her labeling them as "gutter trash" to their faces. The most depth comes from a brief conversation that occurs between Rose and Meg, one of the prostitutes arrested with her:

Rose: How did you get mixed up in this?

Meg: I don't know. Things were bad at home. I ended up in Miami. It just happened.

Rose: Nothing could be bad enough at home for you to end up doing what you're doing.

Meg: I don't need a lecture.

Rose: But you can't be happy with your life.

Meg: I don't wanna talk about it.

Rose: If you ever wanna talk, you know, neighbor to neighbor, I'm here (Fanaro & Nathan, 1986).

The episode does not push a radical message by any means; it does not in any way legitimize sex work as an actual profession in the way activists today are pushing for it. By the episode's end, Meg tells Rose that she is returning home for a second chance at life, mostly motivated by not wanting to end up like Rose (being her age and "still in the business"). However, it does take a step forward in normalization by at the very least humanizing Meg as a prostitute and having the

gall to comment on it at all. It gives her the slightest backstory, justifying her decisions by attributing them to rough conditions. Its popularity amongst the rest of the series is owed to the comedy that surrounds it: Rose’s trademark tangents about her experiences in her hometown of St. Olaf, Minnesota, Sophia’s blunt demeanor, and Dorothy’s status as the exasperated straight man.

Figure 8

Dorothy (center right) prepares to square off with an escort she was arrested with.

Note. Hughes, T., (1986).

These comedic elements come together to form the backbone of the show, with topical issues always shrouded in a humorous way that makes their delivery more receptive to audiences. Another example is in the season 2 episode “Isn’t It Romantic?” (tied for the top rated episode of the show with “Ladies of the Evening”), which features Dorothy’s friend Jean, who is a lesbian, staying at the house and unexpectedly falling in love with Rose (Duteil, 1986). The episode is one among several in the show’s history that deals with LGBT themes, but chooses to handle it with grace. Indeed, the show subverts homophobic comedy that would be considered low hanging fruit. The most blatant example is when Blanche is shocked when she finds out

Jean's sexuality, not because she is gay, but because she cannot believe that Jean would be attracted to Rose and not her. Contemporary critics have since lauded the show for Jean's portrayal as an LGBT character whose sexuality is never the butt of the joke. The show hammers the theme of acceptance home with a trademark one-liner from Sophia upon being asked about her reaction if her child came out as gay: "I wouldn't love him one bit less; I would wish him every happiness. Now keep your fat mouth shut so I can get some sleep" (Duteil, 1986). These episodes, which identified themselves as the show's best through Nielsen ratings or critical acclaim, serve as only a small taste of the show's ability to make meaningful commentary on topical issues. During an era characterized by homophobia and fear (such as AIDS being attributed to gay men and Bill Clinton's "Don't Ask, Don't Tell" policy allowing LGBT people to join the army as long as they kept their sexuality a secret), the show offered an empathetic portrayal through humor. True to form, *The Golden Girls* handled topical issues with grace, especially in the context of issues relating to the LGBT community and other matters of sexuality.

The Cosby Show

The Cosby Show depicted the Huxtables, an upper-middle class family living in New York. The series proved to be one of the main pop culture icons of the era, earning various accolades (e.g. TV's biggest hit in the 80s) and sharing the honor of being the only one of two sitcoms in the history of the Nielsen ratings to be ranked number-one for five consecutive years (TV Talking Heads, 2017). The general wholesomeness of the series as a whole is best exemplified by the season 2 episode "Happy Anniversary", which was included in *TV Guide's* 100 Greatest Episodes of All Time at the turn of the century (*TV Guide*, 1997). The episode hardly features any conflict as the Huxtables put in an effort to make Cliff's parents' 49th

wedding anniversary special, the extent of which is merely Rudy (the youngest Cosby child) spoiling the surprise (Shoenman, 1985). It is in essence, a 22 minute party filled with nothing but smiles. The family's affluence is on full display as they discuss the various gifts prepared for the grandparents, from a commissioned painting to a three week cruise in Europe. The success of the Huxtables, led by the well-off Cliff (an obstetrician, played by Bill Cosby himself) and Clair (a lawyer) comes as a manifestation of Cosby's desire to advance race relations by portraying that black middle-class families were just like their white counterparts (Whitaker, 2011). The American Dream (the capitalist ideal that opportunity is available to any and all Americans who are willing to work in order to achieve their aspirations) was depicted as being possible for everyone, transcending negative ideologies of Blacks. There is no hard-hitting commentary present in the episode, but its general premise displays a common theme of the decade with an emphasis on luxury expenses and an overall optimism about social mobility as a result of capitalism.

Another season 2 episode, "Theo's Holiday", is an excellent example of the way that "real-life lessons" were shrouded in comedy in a way that was both humorous and informational. Theo Huxtable confidently states that he will have no problem making it in "the real world", claiming that getting a job and an apartment will be a breeze (Williams, 1986). The rest of the family then conspire to teach him a lesson, transforming the house overnight into a microcosm of the adult world and throwing Theo into it with nothing more than 2 thousand dollars. Theo's constant struggle to get a job, secure an apartment, buy furniture, and even eat is humorous as he learns the hard way the difficulties of living independently. The comedy is elevated by how seriously the rest of the family take their various roles in the scheme, their intense commitment to the bit being ridiculously funny.

The heaviest one of the three, “Off To See The Wretched” is a diversion from the show’s norm as it features Vanessa Huxtable and her friends sneaking behind their parents’ backs to see a concert in Baltimore. Their trip spirals out of control as they face car theft, con artists, and pickpockets all while their deception unravels; their claim that they would be staying at a friend’s house contradicts news reports of a major fire that happens nearby (St. Germain, 1990). The plot is wrapped up when Clair unleashes fury on her daughter, telling her that it will take a very long time to restore their trust in her. The episode is hardly funny, the majority of the comedic relief coming from Cliff’s unrelated interactions with his granddaughter Olivia. There is no redemption for Vanessa and hardly a satisfying conclusion, portraying a more obvious-than-usual commentary on the dangers of teenagers’ attempts to be fully independent. Latchkey kids, children who came home from school with no supervision due to both parents working, became more prevalent in the 70s and 80s due to the increase in divorce rates and mothers in the workplace. Cliff and Clair are not divorced, but their lucrative and demanding careers categorize their children as latchkey kids, especially when taking into consideration the fact that the higher the education of the parents, the higher the likelihood of latchkey children (Toch & Frady, 1984). Through their aforementioned episodes of focus, Theo and Vanessa portray a timeless idea that teenagers think they are completely capable of functioning without their parents. However, the context of the world at the time—an era of increased spending and frivolous fun—further paints them as latchkey kids with a myopic view of their efficiency as independent adults. The episode is an attempt at heavier-handed commentary as Vanessa and her friends are depicted as being irresponsible for the sake of having fun. Overall, the general premise of *The Cosby Show* is entrenched in the idea that the American Dream is possible as its characters enjoy the wealth and

consumerism of the era, but certain episodes also acknowledge a disconnect between its possibilities and reality.

Roseanne

Roseanne distinguishes itself from the rest of the sitcoms of the era due to its focus on the Conner family and friends, an ensemble composed of only the working class. Unlike the other families mentioned so far, such as the affluent Huxtables of New York and the dubiously wealthy Golden Girls of Miami, Roseanne Conner and her family were deeply seated in suburban Illinois, working blue-collar jobs in the service or manufacturing industries. The premise of the show alone is notable due to its unpretentious sobriety in contrast to the popular themes of opulence and luxury at the time. The Connors were clearly working class and shown to be barely scraping by, evident by running jokes that poke fun at their limited options to eat. Much of the humor was reliant on the family's proneness to squabbling and their sardonic quips in response to the monotony of life, Roseanne leading the choir with her sarcastic drone as its matriarch. Though they bordered on dysfunction, a clear sense of love and care was present in the household, which meant that the family's stability was never in question (Butler in Newcomb, 1997).

Of the chosen episodes to analyze (which were again, determined to be the best of the show's run), the season five two-parter "Crime and Punishment" and "War and Peace" are evident of the show's ability to tackle harder issues while still being enveloped in humor, a combination that makes the medicine go down smoother. "Crime and Punishment" begins as Roseanne's sister Jackie is shown to be temperamental and jittery out of nowhere, which causes concern in Roseanne. Later that night her daughter Darlene later walks in on Jackie accidentally, shocked and puzzled at the large bruises on her back. Upon bringing it up to her mother, Roseanne then prods Jackie for the cause of her injuries, checks her back, and is stunned when

she confesses that her boyfriend Fisher had assaulted her. Roseanne tells Dan what had happened when he walks in; when the sisters move from the kitchen to the living room, Dan slips out of the house with quiet determination. The episode ends with Dan getting arrested after having beat Fisher to avenge Jackie; he complies with the police, who feel bad for having to detain him (Rasmussen, 1993).

“War and Peace” sees Dan quickly bailed out by the family with no trouble and the aftermath between Jackie and Fisher. Roseanne convinces her to end the relationship and goes with her to move her things out of their apartment; when Fisher shows up and begs for forgiveness, Roseanne realizes that this is not Fisher’s first time assaulting Jackie and berates him before leaving. After this, Jackie gains the resolve needed to formally terminate their relationship for good, recognizing that the cycle of abuse never ends and that she needed to remove herself from it (Heline & Heisler, 1993). The episodes are more serious in tone than surrounding ones, as they commentate on the nature of domestic violence and abuse. The heavier moments that deal with the severity of the situation are sandwiched between Roseanne’s trademark sardonic humor and delivery as well as that of the rest of the family. The fact that lower-income women like Jackie are 3.5 times more likely to experience domestic violence grounds the plotlines in reality; they deal with real human experiences, only elevated by comedy from the ensemble cast (Reis, 2019). The episodes are still wildly entertaining, particularly a moment in “War and Peace” where Roseanne and Dan celebrate by finally becoming “white trash” due to the rumors, but jokes like these serve to alter the space for the more poignant scenes to resonate with audiences. Once they’ve permeated the scene, the jokes resume as a means of bringing back optimism. Furthermore, an interesting point is that although Dan technically committed a crime by assaulting Fisher, it is worth mentioning that he is never at any

point antagonized for his actions. It is a case of giving someone a taste of their own medicine; the lightheartedness of Dan's annoyance at Darlene's relishing of the situation coupled with the rumors that spread throughout town (e.g. Dan beating up several men in various scenarios) overall humorously portray the sense that his actions are justified. The show even acknowledges the frequent moral dissonance of adulthood by having the youngest Conner child DJ ask his father why it is okay for adults to lie yet not for kids, or why it is more acceptable to hit a man (Fisher) than a woman (Jackie). In this particular set of circumstances, the show clearly sides with Dan in terms of the ethics involved with confronting someone with intent of vengeance.

As the series goes on, the Conners show upwards mobility, going from firmly blue-collar, passing through the middle class, and finally settling with the wealthy elite after Roseanne wins the lottery in season 9. From there, the show began to lose its roots as episodes were filled with bizarre escapades that centered around their new socioeconomic status. Declining ratings that dragged the show down until its tenth and final season exemplify how viewers mostly resonated with the relatability of the family's social class more than anything (James, 1997). During primetime blocks filled with fresh princes and golden girls, portrayals of lavish lifestyles were oversaturating the airwaves; what made the Conners stand out from all the other families at the time was a sense of authenticity that its surrounding shows failed to offer (James, 1997). Though they represent an ideal that America thought was fully possible in the context of capitalism's "triumph" over communism, *Roseanne's* success in its heyday further demonstrates the dissonance between the world Americans dreamed about in the 80s and 90s and the one they truly lived in.

Friends

Friends lived up to its title and more, with Monica, Rachel, Ross, Phoebe, Chandler, and Joey becoming the new pals of millions of viewers across America. The show remains a cultural institution to this day, often regarded as one of history's best television shows by several institutions such as the Writer's Guild of America and *TIME* (Poniewozie, 2007). Though episode analysis did not yield any outstanding results in terms of commentary on any particular norms at the time, the show's overall premise still acts as a reflection of life and society at the time. Adhering to the theme of socioeconomic security, the protagonists all live comfortable lives in New York City despite their employment; Ross's job as a paleontologist is justifiable (and explains why he lives in a separate apartment), but everyone else's ability to afford lovely Manhattan apartments with jobs like waitress, chef, or struggling actor raised a few eyebrows. It was never something highlighted or acknowledged throughout the series, but the audience's willing suspension of disbelief is another example of how as a nation America was relishing in its booming capitalist economy, boosted by globalization and complemented by the fact that the most significant communist country had succumbed to the free market; in the world of television, with an economy like the United States', social mobility and success was possible for anyone and everyone, even if you were a bit actor (that gets mostly insignificant roles) or whatever Phoebe happened to be doing at a given moment.

Figure 9

Phoebe (center) undergoes in vitro fertilization to become a surrogate mother to her half-brother's child.

Note. Bright, K.S., (1998).

Rather than choosing to comment on contemporary issues, the series chose to go the more wholesome and pleasant route, evident by its most popular episodes. “The One With the Embryos” is a season 4 episode that is often regarded as one of the show's best (if not the definitive), due to the plot and pacing (Condon & Toomin, 1998). The episode is titled for Phoebe’s main plot as she prepares for an in vitro fertilization (IVF) procedure that will allow her to be the surrogate mother for her half-brother and his wife’s baby (Figure 9). It makes no commentary on her decision to do so (some occurred in the previous episode), but at the time the idea of surrogacy was hardly explored in sitcoms, if at all; it can be argued that the treatment of the topic was a step forward for its normalization, since IVF was still fairly new at the time (the first IVF birth only occurring in 1978) (Miller, 2018; BBC News, 1978). If there were any viewers apprehensive about the procedure as a viable means of procreating, their qualms would have been assured, as such a prominent and likable character as Phoebe was shown to be successful, endearing, and hilarious throughout the process. Though the IVF plot is heartwarming and wholesome, the episode is elevated to icon status with its subplot between the rest of the friends: a battle-of-the-sexes quiz show between Monica, Rachel, Joey, and Chandler that was moderated by Ross. What begins as a low-stakes bet of 100 dollars increases

exponentially as their competitiveness ramps up; at the episode's climax these are the stakes: if the girls win, the boys have to get rid of their pet chick and duck, and if the boys win, they would get the girls' apartment. At the episode's climax, Monica and Rachel lose the tiebreaker lightning round due to an inability to name Chandler's job (a running joke that contributed to the question of how he and Joey afforded their apartment). The show doubles down on their stakes and follows through, with the apartment swap occurring at the end. What makes the episode so memorable in the minds of viewers was the balance between the two high-stakes plotlines: Phoebe is stressed at the low success rates of IVF, something that she only has one chance at, while the rest of the cast battles it out for Monica's beloved apartment. As journalist and *Friends* historian Kelsey Miller (2018) puts it, "it balances high-pitch humor with high-stakes emotional drama", the latter taking precedence at the end; in the midst of the rest of the cast arguing about the results of the bet Phoebe interrupts with the announcement that she is indeed pregnant, ending in a group hug that dissipates the anger immediately. *Friends's* best episode is the quintessential example of how wholesome friendly love was the key to surviving life in the big city—not just in the show itself, but in television as a whole; the underlying assumption of the characters' financial security in a time of rapid globalization and the rise of technology cemented its place in the zeitgeist as well.

Cheers, Seinfeld, and Everybody Loves Raymond

Cheers, Seinfeld, and Everybody Loves Raymond were all cultural icons of the era, especially the former two which shared the same defining characteristic of the main cast being portrayed as a sort of "found family", one bound by ties of friendship rather than blood.

However, they are aggregated in this argument for the reasons of an overall lack of

hyper-specific commentary in the episodes chosen for analysis. Nevertheless, they are still reflections of society during the era due to their general premises.

A cultural touchstone of the 1980s and early 90s, *Cheers* centered itself around the titular bar in Boston and its denizens, employees (such as owner Sam Malone and waitresses Carla Tortelli and Diane Chambers) and customers (like Norm Peterson and Cliff Clavin) alike. It is similar to *Roseanne* in the sense that the protagonists are working class, with the exception of Diane—whose roots are in high academia—and psychiatrist Frasier Crane, her love interest who later becomes a bar regular. Of the episodes chosen for analysis, none had any glaring commentary; the season 5 episode “Thanksgiving Orphans” is particularly regarded as one of the show’s best due to the character dynamics and its climax. Sam, Cliff, Norm, Frasier, Diane, and Woody (another bartender introduced in season 4) all find themselves at Carla’s home for Thanksgiving given their lack of plans. Tension slowly rises at the dinner table when Diane insists on waiting for Norm’s turkey to finish cooking before eating; time passes and the rest of the food has gone cold, resulting in a spat between Norm and Carla over who is at fault. The argument culminates with a table-wide food fight as everyone unleashes their anger on each other (Eichen & Steinkeller, 1986). Audiences relished in the catharsis of the characters as they flung stuffing and sides at each other, to the extent that TV Guide ranked it among its top 10 greatest episodes of all time (*TV Guide*, 1997). Though the show hardly contained any biting satire or overt commentary of topical issues, it certainly lived up to its chipper title as an overall wholesome comedy that centered around a “found family” of coworkers.

Touted as “The Show About Nothing”, *Seinfeld* epitomized the slice-of-life aspect of the sitcom, often focusing on minutiae and characters leading lives “of quiet absurdity” (). The titular Jerry Seinfeld and his three friends George, Elaine, and Kramer enjoy their lives in New

York as they intervene in each others', usually with unfortunate consequences. Similar to *The Golden Girls* and *Friends*, the characters' means for affording their comfortable lifestyles in New York City is hardly explained. Jerry is at first a rising stand up comedian, but is never shown to be in financial stress; Elaine and George change jobs frequently, and Kramer is unemployed for much of the series, yet always has money when he needs it. This furthers the established theme of general affluence and socioeconomic comfort that pervaded the airwaves at the time. Again, none of the iconic episodes chosen for analysis carried any hard-hitting commentary, but this is not to say that the show shied away from it entirely. Seeing that covering taboo topics would likely stir up controversy as a result of their portrayal, it is no surprise that those episodes would not be the most popular in the run, and therefore not be included when selecting episodes of interest. Of those selected, "The Contest" proved to be a controversial episode at the time of its airing, due to the titular contest wherein the four main characters compete to see who can go the longest without masturbating (a word that is never outright said, but nevertheless a topic that is taboo) (David, 1992).

For a show that is seemingly about nothing, *Seinfeld* certainly did not abstain from commentary, shrouding it in comedy and sometimes deeply entrenched metaphors. The show's self-promotion as being about nothing allowed for more taboo topics to slip under the radar as they were presented as mundane issues. The season 5 episode "The Couch" does so in a precarious way as it deals with the hotly-debated issue of abortion (something that is still widely contested to this day). Elaine is devastated to find out that a prospective love interest is anti-abortion, while Kramer and a friend start a make-your-own pizza restaurant. An argument arises wherein people debate on what makes a pizza a pizza before it goes into the oven, which fits perfectly with the show's humor due to its frequent overblown focus on disproportionate

topics. However, it ties in perfectly to the more obvious discussion sparked by Elaine's circumstances. If audiences were not already thinking about their stances on abortion, the pizza metaphor achieves the same thing, albeit in a more abstract sense (Duran, 2017). In the context of the episode, the pizza debate is merely nothing more; however, beyond the fourth wall, the show ponders the question of whether or not a fetus inside a woman is considered a life that would be ended due to abortion. Though analysis did not yield any results on how *Seinfeld* commented on contemporary issues, deeper research revealed that the show did not hold back on doing so, though they often alienated viewers for justifiable reasons.

As the final series of the era to chronologically premiere, *Everybody Loves Raymond* ushered in the new millennium as a remnant of television of the 90s. As with the other aforementioned shows, none of the chosen episodes for analysis yielded any particularly outstanding commentary, but its general wholesomeness during a time of rapid growth and transitions proved popular for American audiences who took solace in another simple family sitcom. The show centers on the Barone family, headed by Ray and Debra, while also equally focusing on their fickle relationship with Ray's family (his parents and older brother) who live across the street. The evolution of television portrayals of societal norms has come a long way since the 50s; although Ray and Debra helm the nuclear family prized in *The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet* and *The Danny Thomas Show*, Ray's proximity to his extended family make them essentially part of the household, more resembling the larger family normalized in part by *The Addams Family*. On the other hand, the show is noticeably less progressive as others of its time in certain aspects; namely the fact that Debra left her career in public relations to become a housewife after marrying Ray. However, like *Roseanne*, it is clear that it sustained popularity and acclaim through the late 90s and early 2000s due to the Barone family's relatability. Both shows

center on a family with incredibly dry humor as they navigate the minutiae of life. Though the Barones are not inexplicably wealthy like some of the other aforementioned families, they are not firmly working class either (evident by their stability with only one working parent). The show's tone and atmosphere acts as a sort of middle ground between the firmly blue-collar Connors and the upper-class Huxtables as Ray and his family live comfortably in the suburbs of Long Island. In the same vein of *Roseanne*, *Everybody Loves Raymond* portrayed a more realistic family in terms of socioeconomic status, which proved to be refreshing for Americans during a time when wealth was considered to be a possible outcome for many.

The 00s–10s: 9/11 and National Coping

Historical Context

December 31, 1999 was a horizon of many things for the United States; in literal terms, it brought a new year, a new decade, a new century, and a new millennium. However if there was one word to describe what the 2000s signaled in the country, it would be uncertainty. Even the first minute of the new millennium was plagued with anxiety; after the advent and evolution of computers in the latter half of the 20th century, the country had grown reliant on them for many things, from power plants to banks to airlines. Since years had been coded as their last two digits (e.g. “70” would translate to 1970), in the final years of the 1990s programmers suddenly became worried about the prospect of equipment shutting down due to a failure to recognize “00” as 2000, instead interpreting it as 1900 (Rutledge et al., 2022). The notion spiraled out of control, scaring the general public as the “Y2K bug” (“Year 2 Thousand”) threatened infrastructural collapse and armageddon. Fortunately, the hysteria had no foundation in truth, as the world largely continued as normal when the clock struck twelve on January 1, 2000.

The following year would not bring any respite either, as a singular day brought about a seismic shift that would change the country forever. On September 11, 2001, a group of militants associated with the Islamic extremist group al-Qaeda hijacked several American planes with the intent of crashing them into various locations. Two planes crashed into the Twin Towers in New York City, with another crashing into the Pentagon in Washington, D.C., and another in Pennsylvania. In all, the attacks yielded a casualty count of almost 3000 people (composed of mostly civilians, first responders, and all of the hijackers), making it the deadliest terrorist attack on U.S. soil and in human history. It was the catalyst for the ensuing Global War on Terror, wherein America led the charge against terrorism around the world, primarily in the middle east (George W. Bush Presidential Library, n.d.). In the aftermath, American comedy went dark; late-night comedy shows were suspended, satirical magazines were not published, even light-hearted cartoons (such as that of *The New Yorker*; children's programming was largely unaffected) were absent. Overall, Americans felt like "humor was inappropriate and laughter was impossible in times of such shock and grief" (Kuipers in Gournelos & Greene, 2011). When *Saturday Night Live (SNL)*—an institution in American comedy—aired two weeks later, rather than its usual satirical cold open, a performance by Paul Simon opened the show, with Mayor Rudolph Giuliani and a few first responders following up with a few words; after a long pause, showrunner Lorne Michaels awkwardly asked him, "Can we be funny?". Giuliani's brief response of "Why start now?" (humorously implying that *SNL* was never funny to begin with) seemingly broke the tension, relieving the audience and allowing them to enjoy themselves (Gournelos & Greene, 2011).

In the following months, America was slowly finding that the nation needed humor in dark times; a key characteristic of American thinking of humor was the belief in its healing

power during times of strife and this was often invoked in the following years (Kuipers in Gournelos & Greene, 2011). Comedy about the attacks began almost immediately after, with people admitting that dark jokes about the event were one of the first things that made them laugh again; it's likely that these on-the-nose references served as a coping strategy to a shaken nation. Dark humor went on to define the decade, with different manifestations depending on the medium; disaster jokes were prevalent on the internet while late-night television hosts relied on satire (Gurney, Kuipers in Gournelos & Greene, 2011). In general, commentary was now rarely the forefront of special episodes, but now deeply entrenched in the foundation of the show's premise. Reflections of society are much more subliminal as they are buried under layers of subtext rather than presented upfront like in shows of the mid-twentieth century. Therefore, much of the following analyses do not come from the isolated episodes, but rather from the shows' structure and premise; where applicable, further research was then done to isolate particularly outstanding (though not necessarily the best) episodes that portrayed more obvious commentary.

As for sitcoms, their general premises remained the same, often focusing on the dynamics within a family or workplace; however, what distinguished shows from the era from its predecessors was a subgenre of sitcom that grew in popularity: the mockumentary (a portmanteau of "mock" and "documentary"). This happened in tandem with the rising interest in reality television programs like *Survivor* and *Big Brother*, a phenomenon whose success was grounded in fascination with the real lives of outrageous characters (Perjurer, 2021). With the popularization of the mockumentary came a different type of humor as well, cringe comedy, which is derived from the painful yet humorous awkwardness of social interaction and people's lack of self-awareness (Susman, 2013). It is often done so via the mockumentary due to its use of

single-camera shooting (and the absence of a laugh track); it is reliant on the deafening silence in-universe that lingers after a tasteless joke, which then prompts laughter from the audience. As analysis proves, the protagonists of these mockumentaries are usually unlikable egotists, and the format goes on to highlight their flaws by juxtaposing them alongside “normal”, straight-laced people (McFarlane, 2009). As time went on, commentary became more entrenched in the shows’ underlying foundations rather than expressed outright in episodes, coming a long way from the less-subtle sitcoms of the mid-twentieth century. The combination of the mockumentary format, cringe humor, and a recent national tragedy synergized to manifest some of the best sitcoms of all time, all while still reflecting the state of the nation at this point, during a time of uncertainty. As time passed and the country grew further removed from the tragedy, the types of humor and subgenres remained, but subject focus then turned to the state of modern society, from the ubiquity of technology to the growing diversity of its citizens.

Case Studies

Arrested Development

Premiering in 2003, *Arrested Development* was the first of the shows of interest to utilize the mockumentary format, and the one chronologically closest to the September 11 attacks. The series focuses on the formerly wealthy and dysfunctional Bluth family after George Bluth Sr. (the patriarch and CEO of the family real estate company) gets arrested and jailed for embezzlement. Its premise follows his son Michael as he struggles to restore credibility to the company while juggling familial issues. True to the format, almost everyone in the main ensemble cast is highly unlikable. Mockumentaries thrive off of the juxtaposition of the obviously insensitive protagonist and the straight men; it just so happens that the ratio here is flipped. Michael and his

son George Michael are the only voices of reason while the rest of the family (his parents, siblings, and nieces and nephews) are unintentional obstacles in his mission to simply stay afloat.

The dark humor that arose out of the tragedy was a staple of the show from the very beginning. One of its best, “Pier Pressure” displayed delightfully dark comedy as audiences are compelled to laugh at the Bluth way of parenting (Hurwitz & Valley, 2004). To show how awful of a father George Sr. was to his kids, several flashbacks detail the various times he tried to teach inane lessons to them with the help of an amputated family friend. George Sr. would contrive scenarios that would lead to the maiming of said amputee, to which he would deliver the intended moral. For example, one of the kids had finished a carton of milk and had forgotten to leave a note saying so, meaning George Sr. would not have known to stop by the store on the way home. During the car trip to get one, he “hits” a pedestrian (the amputated accomplice), whose prosthetic arm hits the windshield. As the kids scream in terror, he makes his way to the rear window, which rolls down before he utters the lesson to be learned: “And that’s why you always leave a note”. This episode in particular is reminiscent of the disaster jokes that took place soon after the 9/11 attacks, wherein people would find a way to humorize the awful events that had just occurred (Kuipers, in Gournelos & Greene, 2011) . However, instead of the deaths of 3000 people, it is one man’s false arm.

As a response to current events, the absurdity of the show’s plotlines actually serve as effective satire of the Bush administration once the Global War on Terror began. A recurring plotline embedded throughout the show is a shady business deal that George Sr. was attempting to hide, which is revealed to be agreements with Saddam Hussein (president/dictator of Iraq at the time, whose administration the U.S. succeeded in deposing). The end of season one reveals that he had a business deal to construct Bluth houses in Iraq, effectively deeming him a

traitor. An analysis of the season two episode “Good Grief” foremostly shows a continuation of the treason arc; the Bluths are led to believe that George Sr. (who had escaped prison and was on the lam) was murdered in a Mexican prison (Levenstein, 2004). The family then decides to hold a wake in his honor, but George Michael ends up finding him hiding in a hole next to the house, checking his immaculate teeth as proof of identity (Figure 10). This final plot point mirrors the actual discovery of Hussein, who was found in an underground hideout; the dental inspection parallels US methods of identifying his sons (*Associated Press*, 2003; Boyle, 2003). The fact that a main character has a proven tie to terrorism and follows an arc that mirrors that of a symbolic figure of terrorism is absurd. A concept like this that is only two years removed from the greatest terrorist attack in history theoretically should be considered distasteful, and yet it worked. The establishment of George Sr. as an objectively bad person and Michael’s (whose straight man perspective grounds the show) exasperated attempts to forgive him present a humorous foundation that the show lays on. With each episode, Michael finds a new reason to leave his family forever, yet his optimism and good intentions always keep him in Orange County. The absurdity of the concept that is applied to relatively normal people (a family business as compared to the head of state of Iraq) effectively satirizes global geopolitical events on a microscopic scale, which makes it all the funnier.

Figure 10

George Sr. is discovered hiding in a hole underneath the house, similar to Saddam Hussein.

Note. Melman, J., (2004).

The show certainly did not try to deny its references to the ongoing wars in the Middle East; a season one episode is titled “Shock and Aww”, a clear nod to the phrase “shock and awe” which described the first night of American military presence in Iraq in March 2003 (Doherty & Kiley, 2023). Further research into other episodes reveal even more satirization of the various political events that occurred during the war. In the season two episode “Sad Sack” (which immediately follows “Good Grief”), a prosecutor is confident in the idea that George Sr. did indeed build houses for Saddam Hussein, but also that the collaboration went far deeper; he posits that George Sr. built houses on hills over underground facilities that housed weapons of mass destruction (WMDs), aiding Hussein in covering up a potential threat to American security (Adler, 2004). He invokes the recent Patriot Act in order to gain access to the Bluth’s records, which include a photo of said houses in Iraq. The landmark legislation was passed in the following months of the 9/11 attacks and was meant to improve counter-terrorism efforts by allowing the federal government to heighten surveillance for the sake of national security. This included the ability to ask for a court order to obtain business records, which is precisely what happens in the episode (U.S. Department of Justice, n.d.). The episode comes to its climax when the photo of Bluth houses over Iraqi hills supposedly concealing WMDs is broadcast on the

news, gaining the attention of the highest levels of the federal government and military. The frenzy caused by confirmed proof of a once-powerful domestic terrorist is then immediately halted when officials everywhere realize that the picture did not show any hills or weapons. Instead they were a close-up picture of Tobias Fünke's (George Sr.'s son-in-law) testicles, taken by accident. The entire episode is ludicrous, but it was surprisingly not far from reality. In the first several months of the Global War on Terror, Vice President Dick Cheney was absolutely certain that Hussein was pushing to develop a nuclear arsenal to use against the United States, that there was a fleet of WMDs ready for deployment. However, as with George Sr. (yet another bizarre yet confusingly funny parallel between the two), there was no evidence that Hussein and Iraq possessed any WMDs, nor were developing a plan to obtain them (Corn, 2013). As journalist Asawin Suebsaeng (2013) wrote for *Mother Jones*, in anticipation for the invasion of Iraq, "the Bush White House presented—and much of the press and public bought—evidence that was so shaky they might as well have been waving around a blurry photo of some balls".

Even at the show's most ridiculous, *Arrested Development* was always grounded in the context of America's paranoia, ever so amplified by its war of vengeance. Its commentary on current events was an absurd satire on par with *M*A*S*H* about the pointlessness of war, only now it was underscored by distrust and fear as a result of an attack on domestic soil.

The Office

For many Americans, perhaps the most salient example of the mockumentary sitcom in recent years is *The Office*. While it is not the first show of analysis to be adapted from a British sitcom (*All In The Family* was adapted from *Til Death Us Do Part*), both found their rhythm and went on to distinguish themselves from their source material and sustain a long and healthy run. Again, true to the medium, the series documents the daily lives of the workers of the Scranton

branch of Dunder Mifflin Paper Company, headed by their inept boss Michael Scott. Michael is immature and unprofessional, and much of the show's antics stem from his desire to make the workplace fun rather than productive. He and his sycophantic assistant (and salesman) Dwight Schrute are often juxtaposed against the rest of the office, who act as straight men to their shenanigans. While *Arrested Development* used the dysfunctional family dynamic to satirize geopolitical events, *The Office* instead uses the workplace setting to satirize corporate culture at this point in American history. In addition, *The Office* differed in its storytelling techniques from *Arrested Development* in terms of how character motivations were revealed. The latter employed the use of an omniscient narrator who was aware of the states of the characters, while the former employed talking heads, an interview technique wherein subjects speak of their true feelings directly to the camera. The popularity of the show would pave the way for future series to employ the same technique, regardless of if the documentary was real in-universe, such as *Parks and Recreation* and the soon-to-be-discussed *Modern Family*.

In an attempt to faithfully reproduce the try tone and atmosphere of the original British series for American audiences, some of the show's best cringe comedy comes in its first season. "Diversity Day" depicts a seminar that everyone in the office is forced to attend due to Michael's constant recitation of a Chris Rock stand up routine. Michael is offended by this and afterwards helms his own seminar, encouraging everyone to reenact racial stereotypes in an attempt to purge them from the space. One of the jokes especially dates the episode, as Michael explains in a talking head the reason for not including a certain ethnicity: "You'll notice I didn't have anybody be an Arab. I thought that would be too explosive. No pun intended. But I just thought. 'Too soon for Arabs.' Maybe next year. Um... You know, the ball's in their court" (Novak, 2005). The joke is an obvious reference to the September 11 attacks and the fact that many did not know

when it would be okay to make light of the events. As mentioned earlier however, it did not take very long since it was seen as a coping mechanism. Similar to Archie and *All In The Family*, the show makes it clear that despite the fact that Michael is one of the protagonists, viewers would be ill-advised if they shared the same beliefs as him. The rest of the office demonstrates this as they try their best to obey their boss while being non-offensive. Receptionist Pam Beesley clearly states her intentions when Michael asks her to “stir the pot”, saying, “Okay. If I have to do this, based on stereotypes that are totally untrue, that I do not agree with, you would maybe not be a very good driver.” (Novak, 2005). As an innocent man with tendencies of bigotry, Michael’s character is an interesting subversion of people (both real and fictional) who draw on offensive humor. While his intentions may be good, his often selfish motivations for employing activities like this (in this case, it is to prove that he is politically correct in response to being told he is not) manifest them in ways that are questionable. In a more specific context, Michael genuinely thinks that acting out racist stereotypes is a helpful way to exercise tolerance towards diversity, yet in doing so comes across as the exact opposite by encouraging the boiling down of ethnicities to offensive monoliths. This trope of “political over-correctness” combined with innocent bigotry continues throughout the show and across other sitcoms as well as America continues to terms with its growing diversity.

The show’s chosen episodes for analysis have proved to be its best for comedy reasons rather than particularly biting commentary or satire; for example, “Stress Relief” begins with a cold open about a fire drill that goes horrendously wrong, ending with an employee having a heart attack. However, further research into other episodes reveals statements on more specific aspects of office politics. The season two episode “Boys and Girls” depicts a surprising statement on the extent to which companies will prevent the formation of unions. Jan Levinson, an

employee at Dunder Mifflin's corporate headquarters, conducts a seminar with the women of the office, which spurs Michael to conduct one with its men. His antics result in the trashing of the Dunder Mifflin warehouse, which inspires its crew to form a union. When Jan gets word about a union forming within the company, she threatens to have the branch shut down in retaliation. The episode's events have been analyzed from a legal standpoint and according to American Rights at Work, Jan's threats are illegal, yet rooted in reality, as almost half of employers threaten to close a worksite when workers try to unionize (American Rights at Work, 2007.).

Though the show is about the minutiae of office politics and happenings, contemporary writers have commented on its parallels to government politics as well. Writing for *Vanity Fair*, Graydon Carter draws allegorical parallels between Michael and President George Bush and between Dwight and Vice President Dick Cheney. He describes both Michael and Bush as smug, prone to malapropisms, and particularly revelrous in attempts at humor, citing a particular incident where Bush began a correspondent's dinner with a mock inspection of the venue for WMDs as on par with a Scott shenanigan (Carter, 2008). As right-hand-men to their prospective superiors, Dwight and Cheney are characterized as sycophantic, scowling, and "borderline bonkers" (Carter, 2008). Whether or not this was intentional on the writers' behalf is debatable, but the allegory paints another picture of how television reacts in response to the larger social atmosphere of the nation.

The Big Bang Theory

With the new millennium came a slow shift of popularity away from the multi-camera sitcoms that dominated the airwaves of the 20th century to the modern single-camera shows that audiences are now accustomed to. Of the previously discussed shows, almost all were multi-camera series as they were filmed akin to a proshot of a play with a live studio audience,

the only exceptions being *Get Smart* and *M*A*S*H*, which are classified as single-camera series (shot like a movie). Of the most popular shows that emerge from the 21st century, *The Big Bang Theory* sticks out as the only show from the era that retains its multi-camera production style. The show is definitely the most puzzling inclusion of the era, as its consistently high Nielsen ratings (never dipping below 11 million since season 4) garnered intensely negative reviews from critics. To the delight or chagrin of audiences across the United States, it is a fact that the show is certainly quintessential of the era through its normalization of nerd culture that has grown to become mainstream. The show centers on five friends living in Pasadena, California: roommates Sheldon and Leonard work as researchers at CalTech along with their friends Howard and Raj. Their small (though romantically lonely) world of physics and nerd media is shaken up when Penny, an aspiring actress, moves in across the hall from Sheldon and Leonard. Leonard's romantic interest in their new neighbor leads to an unlikely friendship that allows him and his friends to open themselves up to female friends. The show's humor regularly relies on the complete lack of social skills in its main characters (excluding Penny), especially Sheldon (who consistently shows traits of autism spectrum disorder) and their fondness for various aspects of geek culture (including comic books, video games, and board/card games).

None of the chosen episodes of analysis yielded any obvious commentary about the state of society at this point; in a country that grew paranoid, cynical, and sardonic in the wake of 9/11 whose television evolved to reflect it, it is puzzling to see why this almost-esoteric show retained such a strong audience throughout the 2010s when competing with more modern and unique rivals such as *Community*, *Parks and Recreation*, and *Veep*. However, in the show's inherent makeup and structure lies a reasonable explanation when taking into account historical context. The show's fourth season promoted two side characters to the main ensemble, microbiologist

(and Howard's love interest) Bernadette and neurobiologist (and Sheldon's love interest) Amy. As Neima Jahromi (2019) wrote for *The New Yorker*, with the larger ensemble and equal gender balance, "the show's success becomes less of a mystery: it came to resemble *Friends*". Several similarities can be drawn between the two; a scientist falls in love with an ambitious and beautiful woman, the two main settings are apartments across the hall from each other, and an iconic couch (Austerlitz as cited by Jahromi, 2019). Most importantly, as Jahromi (2019) explains:

[B]oth shows reflected and amplified a societal shift that was entering the mainstream. *Friends* thrived at a time when coffee shops, once the haven of leisurely boho sophisticates, were being spread to strip malls by titans like Starbucks. In between sips of coffee, the show captured the new life style of a generation whose members, in their twenties, had put off marriage and children and replaced many of the roles traditionally filled by family with friendship. Likewise, *The Big Bang Theory* introduced concepts from tech and nerd circles as that culture grew from a curiosity to a vexation to an inescapable substrate of American life.

The Big Bang Theory thrived in utilizing an old tried-and-true format and blending it with modern concepts such as geek culture and women in STEM to form an end product that appealed to a wide demographic, particularly those on the older end of the spectrum. The outdated nerd archetypes appeal heavily to its average viewer in their mid-50s (who watches television *on television*), who perhaps finds them more easier to digest compared to the growing complexity of streaming services and social media (Jahromi, 2019). It was rooted in the present, yet it evoked the aura of a simpler time prior to the 9/11 attacks.

Similar to *The Adventures of Ozzie and Harriet*, the show laid a foundation of what was considered to be safe in television (and therefore garnering easy laughs) at this point in time, serving as a baseline for other shows who chose to experiment. Single-camera shows like *Community* and *Silicon Valley*, which were on air in the same decade, would serve as more elevated forms of what *The Big Bang Theory* sought to achieve; audiences and critics lauded *Community*'s more nuanced and accurate portrayal of autism through Abed Nadir compared to Sheldon's stereotypic caricature, while *Silicon Valley* similarly focused on geeks in engineering and was praised for its less cartoonish depiction of "nerds" and the laser accuracy of its setting (Gaeke-Franz, 2022). The show's enduring popularity reflects a different, more aged demographic than the ones previously discussed here that nonetheless reflected America at the time during a period of exponentially growing complexity.

Modern Family

As its title suggests, *Modern Family* is a cornerstone to the evolution of the American family as portrayed in television, depicting vastly different structures from the ones in previous decades (such as the Nelsons and the Addams discussed earlier). The show focuses on three differently structured families all connected by its patriarch Jay Pritchett: Jay has remarried a much younger woman from Colombia (Gloria) with a young child (Manny), representing the blended family; his daughter Claire helms the nuclear family with her husband Phil Dunphy as they care for their three kids (Haley, Alex, and Luke); lastly, Jay's son Mitchell and his partner Cam adopt a baby from Vietnam (Lily), representing a same-sex family. The family tree is a confusing jumble of branches (e.g. Gloria and Claire are roughly the same age but the former is the latter's stepmother, and Manny is the same age as Luke but is actually his step-uncle) but it goes to show how families can become so diverse (spanning multiple generations and ethnic

groups) as a result of the changing views on marriage and child-rearing. The episodic series focuses on the daily troubles of raising children, managing in-laws, and domestic minutiae from the perspectives of all three families. Just the show's premise alone shows how far television has come in terms of portraying the average family of America; Cam and Mitchell's status as main characters and their relationship is a clear progression from the rare mention of a gay character that happened often in the twentieth century. In addition, the inclusion of Gloria, Manny, and Lily reflect the growing percentage of multiracial families in the United States.

One of the top episodes of its eleven season run, "Connection Lost", is not due to any subversive or radical commentary but more so because of its genre-pushing format (Levitan & Ganz, 2015). The plot sees Claire at an airport away from home struggling to contact Haley, who has seemingly gone missing after a fight with her mother. She tries to contact the family in attempts to know her whereabouts, but a series of discoveries leads everyone to believe that she eloped with an ex-boyfriend after discovering that she is pregnant with his child. The episode breaks from the show's mockumentary format by presenting it through Claire's laptop screen as she uses Facetime and social media to not only find Haley (Figure 11), but juggle all of the other tasks brought on by the family. Rather than the usual talking head, Claire's internet activity substitutes insight into her thoughts and motivations in a unique way; it is an excellent portrayal of how the internet and technology have become deeply ingrained in life today. On the role of technology in the show as a whole, producer Abraham Higginbotham explained to *The New York Times* that the writers used to "talk about how cellphones killed the sitcom because no one ever goes to anyone's house anymore" to interact; with *Modern Family*, there was a conscious effort to ingrain it into the story so that it plays an active role, which further reflects society's relationship with technology in the digital age (Feiler, 2011). "Connection Lost" is the most

exemplary episode of this, as technology is the entire framing device for the plot's events. This technique would continue to be popular throughout the decade, most notably with the 2018 film *Searching* following a similar premise (a father trying to find his missing daughter) and using the same framing device of restricting plot events to a computer or phone screen.

Figure 11

The Dunphys finally locate Haley, as seen through Claire's Macbook screen.

Note. Levitan, S., (2015).

In addition, the show's humor largely draws from its multicultural foundations, using it to subvert the low-hanging fruit of racist or stereotypical jokes. One of the show's iconic scenes sees Cam, Mitchell, Gloria, and Lily at lunch in a pho restaurant, with the former three hoping to expose the latter more to her Vietnamese heritage. Lily instead acts up, saying that she hates Vietnam and that she is not Vietnamese, but gay. Mitchell responds by saying that she is not gay, just confused (which horrifies him, since the phrase has been used to deny individuals of their true sexuality). More of the conversation is taken out of context, culminating with Cam agreeing with Gloria's desire to take her kids to Colombia for the summer, saying loudly that "everybody should go back to where they came from" (Ko, 2013). The scene is hilarious, as Cam and

Mitchell somehow offend every minority in the restaurant and even a majority in the span of three minutes. By having a member of a marginalized group (i.e. Cam and Mitchell for the LGBT community) make these statements, there is a layer of irony that enhances the comedy; in addition, Cam's out-of-context quotes pass off as casual racism which elevates the scene to near perfection. In the midst of the LGBT and race jokes, there is a moment of melancholy as Gloria projects her anger about her kids not embracing their culture onto Lily, who is merely a testy child; she worries that she is losing Manny to America as he has forgotten most of his Spanish while her youngest child might not even learn Spanish at all. Gloria's fears are completely valid as she grapples with the concept of immigrants assimilating into the mainstream culture of a new country; institutional racism (like in the educational system) incentivizes assimilation into American culture at the expense of one's native culture in order to truly thrive. The scene may only be three minutes long, with Gloria's admission taking up only a third, but it says quite a lot about the struggles that families in a growingly-diverse America can face in terms of blending different cultures. Overall, *Modern Family* truly lives up to its title as it showcases historically marginalized groups as main characters, highlights the ubiquity of technology in plotlines, and emphasizes the multicultural foundation on which it is built on.

Brooklyn Nine-Nine

As the most recent series chosen for analysis (having premiered in 2013), *Brooklyn Nine-Nine* also reflects the growing diversity of the United States while tackling its complexities as it manifests through interracial interactions. About half of the main cast is played by people of color, which is a more equal balance compared to only three in that of *Modern Family*. The workplace sitcom focuses on the detectives of the 99th precinct of the New York Police Department (NYPD) in Brooklyn as they navigate office minutiae and the more exciting aspects

of the job as police. While previously discussed shows have had their premises act as a reflection of society, *Brooklyn Nine–Nine*'s comes in the form of its characters. The pilot immediately establishes that the 99's commanding officer Raymond Holt is gay, even going as far as acknowledging the discrimination that occurred in the NYPD as a whole. When asked about his coming out, Holt explains:

About 25 years ago. The NYPD was not ready for an openly gay detective. But then the old guard died out. Suddenly, they couldn't wait to show off the fact that they had a highly ranking gay officer. I made Captain. But they put me in a public affairs unit. I was a good soldier. I helped recruitment. But all I ever really wanted was my own command. And now I finally got it. And I'm not gonna screw it up" (Goor & Schur, 2013).

Holt's trademark steely demeanor and deadpan delivery are attributed to years of having to endure discrimination within the NYPD (Reese, 2019). Further on in the show, detective Rosa Diaz gets her own arc involving her bisexuality and the struggles that come with coming out to one's family. While *Modern Family* also had two openly LGBT characters in the form of Mitchell and Cam, the commentary surrounding their sexuality was much more subtle and lighthearted (i.e. more rooted in comedy) compared to that of Holt and Rosa. Given that *Modern Family* debuted four years earlier, it can be argued that Cam and Mitchell normalized the notion of LGBT main characters that allowed for later shows to tackle more heavy commentary. *Brooklyn Nine–Nine* can afford to offer more depth to its LGBT characters and never make their sexuality the punchline of the joke, rather subverting decades of homophobia in TV by mocking it and heteronormativity (Reese, 2019).

None of the episodes chosen for analysis showed any particular commentary; the episodes that came out to be the best of the show's run did so because of comedic merit or

satisfying plotlines. For example, the episodes “HalloVeen” and “Jake and Amy” were chosen for analysis, but their popularity comes from the fact that they were important milestones in the arc of detectives Jake Peralta and Amy Santiago, who get engaged in the former and married in the latter. The third episode chosen, “The Box”, was deemed one of the show’s best due to its fast pace, moderately high stakes, and laser-fast wit as Holt and Jake try to goad a confession out of a suspect with an airtight alibi. However, further research reveals that the show was very much driven by current events, with their controversial nature or heavy-handedness garnering mixed opinions. The season four episode “Moo Moo” handles racial profiling in a graceful way as Sergeant Terry Jeffords is arrested in the neighborhood he lives in simply because of his race (Figure 12). Prior to his encounter with the officer, he was looking for a security blanket that one of his daughters dropped (named Moo Moo, giving the episode its title) and did not have his badge on him to prove his title as a detective. When he later meets with the officer, the latter apologizes for not knowing that Terry was a cop, but not for racially profiling him; as a representation of cops everywhere who justify their acts of racism with the occupation, he responds that he refuses to apologize for “doing his job”. When Holt tries to convince Terry to not file an official complaint (claiming that whistleblowers are shunned by coworkers), Terry stands up for the larger principle, saying,

When I got stopped the other day, I wasn't a cop. I wasn't a guy who lived in the neighborhood looking for his daughter's toy. I was a black man. A dangerous black man. That's all he could see. A threat. And I couldn't stop thinking about my daughters and their future. And how one day they could be walking down the street, looking for their kid's Moo Moo, and get stopped by a bad cop. And they probably won't get to play the

police card to get out of trouble. I don't like that thought. And I'm gonna do something about it (Jackson, 2017).

Terry's experience is heavily rooted in reality; in the surrounding years more and more cases of police brutality towards African Americans have made the news cycles, from the killing of Philando Castile (who was shot several times during a traffic stop) to the shooting of twelve-year-old Tamir Rice in 2014 (*Associated Press*, 2021). The episode premiered on the same night of a ruling in which two officers would not be charged with the killing of Alton Sterling, who was shot during an altercation with police; (Hanna, 2018).

Figure 12

Terry Jeffords (right) is stopped by police for suspicious activity while looking for his child's toy.

Note. Carey, M., (2017).

The episode is still largely humorous, with things like a ditty about racism and Holt's random hatred of a coworker easing the underlying tensions; as Liam Mathews (2017) wrote for *TV Guide*, it is like putting medicine in a pudding cup. With the murder of George Floyd in 2020 (an instance of police brutality in which Floyd was arrested and died when an officer knelt on his neck for almost ten minutes), the show reacted to the social climate by adjusting its eighth season in response to the anti-racism protests. Given that the show revolves around police,

inherently branding them as lovable protagonists, showrunner Dan Goor felt that it needed to take a completely new direction (BBC, 2020). Americans were now rethinking “the merits of shows about benevolent cops”, which meant that the series needed to tread carefully in order to retain its humor and gripping storylines in a way that does not glorify the police, especially considering its reputation (Schube & Mehran, 2020). This sort of mid-production shift for an established series well into its run further displays the cyclical relationship between history, society, and TV; the murder of George Floyd sparked an outstanding response in the public, which forces television to respond as well, hopefully with the intention that society responds kindly in turn as the cycle begins anew. *Brooklyn Nine-Nine*’s heavier commentary exemplifies the role of television in changing the attitudes of its audience through a thoughtful blending of topical issues and humor; its willingness to adapt to society as it responds to historical events also demonstrates the larger role of television in terms of shaping national opinions.

Implications and Future Research

I acknowledge that in my attempts to boil these sitcoms down into their most quintessential episodes (to have a holistic view of their “essence”), my methodology did not always yield the content I needed for analysis. It was an attempt to reconcile the idea that the most popular episodes tend to represent society the most, while also hoping that that representation was built on a foundation of a response to society as well. For many shows, its most popular episodes were due to outstanding commentary in addition to humor, but this was not the case for all of them; in the case of these, their popularity was mostly attributed to the sheer comedy. Further research was done on my part for shows that did not yield commentary from the chosen episodes alone in order to identify the ones that did. The methodology can be

modified to account for this, but I believe it is a good starting point for identifying—at the very least—the most representative episodes of each program.

With this in mind, the methodology and analysis presented here still offer many avenues of future research in the same area. I chose to do a more comprehensive analysis of American sitcoms throughout all of television history, but future scholars may be more interested in analyzing television of a specific era, genre, or theme. For example, the process of choosing the quintessential programs of each decade through cross-referencing lists of different criteria can be applied to dramas, children's TV, or even talk/variety shows. The same type of analysis can be done across history as well, though focusing only on a certain theme. For example, one might be interested in tracing specifically the evolution of the family structure in television throughout the ages, as I touched upon with *The Danny Thomas Show*, *The Addams Family*, and *Modern Family*. Another may be interesting in tracing the portrayal of the LGBT community (as mentioned with *The Golden Girls* and *Brooklyn Nine–Nine*) throughout the ages or that of women (exemplified by *I Love Lucy* and *The Mary Tyler Moore Show*). The techniques employed in this research are an example of a broader look at a single aspect of television history and serves as a baseline to allow for future research to go more into depth about more specific elements.

Figure 13

Ted Lasso's optimism fuels AFC Richmond (left), but his underlying demons manifest themselves as panic attacks off the field (right).

Note. Dunton, E., (2021); Lowney, D., (2020).

In terms of *this* analysis, there is also a future due to the fact that the United States is currently still living through a major historical event, the COVID–19 pandemic. The first global pandemic since the influenza pandemic a century earlier, American life grinded to a half as the country shut down and encouraged everyone to stay inside if not an essential worker. The pandemic affected many aspects of regular life, from grocery shopping to social gatherings. The ensuing anxiety and fear of the “new normal” is reflected in the television of the era as well. Again, like with 9/11, sitcoms used humor to cope with the event; shows like *Superstore* (about a Walmart–esque chain retailer) and the aforementioned *Brooklyn Nine–Nine* worked the pandemic into the shows’ universes to infuse it with light–hearted humor, while others chose not to, taking a more escapist route with events seemingly taking place in one in which it did not happen. However, in terms of the latter, there are still themes present that reflect the needs and norms of society. A brief example of this would be *Ted Lasso*, a dramedy focusing on the titular American college football coach who is hired to manage a Premier League football (i.e. soccer) team in London, a sport he knows nothing about. Though Ted is the archetypal fish out of water, his relentless optimism, positivity, and kindness endear himself and his ideals to a country that had little faith in him. The show is seemingly about football, but as the plot unfolds so do several themes regarding masculinity, self–esteem, and mental health. Mental health is of high

importance in the series, which parallels that of the country at large. As a result of the fear and uncertainty that the world was plunged into, the World Health Organization (2022) reported that more people reported symptoms of psychological distress, such as anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder. The mental health theme is manifested through Ted's anxiety hidden under all of the layers of positivity. The show tracks his journey as he experiences his first panic attack (Figure 13), his later decision to go to therapy, and his progress, destigmatizing the still somewhat taboo topic of mental illness. During a time in the United States filled with dread, uncertainty, and anxiety, viewers welcomed Ted and AFC Richmond (short for Association Football Club) with open arms as their wholesomeness and warmth filled a hole left by the absence of loved ones. In this case, the show reflects society in the sense that it was a response to something that the U.S. desperately craved at this time: hope. It also did comment on topical issues such as mental health and masculinity. The extent to which the show affected the country is best seen in the cast's recent visit to the White House in March of 2023; comedian Jason Sudeikis, the showrunner and Ted himself, spoke on the importance of looking after one another (echoing another theme of the show) and accepting the idea of getting professional help (*Associated Press*, 2023). The invitation comes in support of the mental health part of president Joe Biden's bipartisan "unity agenda", which attempts to fix issues in the country that affect all Americans, regardless of political party. The soaring popularity of *Ted Lasso* in the wake of the pandemic and its effect on American audiences is a current testament to television's ability to affect change on a societal level. Though the 2020s are far from being over, whatever sitcoms come out will still reflect the American experience.

Conclusions

As demonstrated, analyzing the most iconic sitcoms of America since the advent of television has yielded an abridged social history of the nation, grounded in a medium of art that allows hard-hitting commentary while still entertaining. There is a clear cyclical relationship wherein a major historical event causes changes in society, which then spurs television as a whole to react to these new norms; certain series in particular proved to be more popular than others, rising above the rest due to their ability to subtly comment on the zeitgeist while balancing it with palate-cleansing humor. The fact that many of these shows are still household names speaks to their enduring legacy on social history. Others may be forgotten remnants of the past, but their contributions to the medium are long lasting and paved the way for future shows to build upon the progress that they established.

After the triumph of the Allies in World War II, television was part of a large media effort to force women back into the kitchen, though outstanding series proved to subvert the notion while still making audiences laugh. Lucille Ball challenged preconceived notions of femininity while Dick Van Dyke portrayed a refreshingly healthy marital relationship, both doing so using their trademark slapstick humor. As the nation shifted into its next era, the tense Cold War, television took the opportunity to comment on American ideals both inside its borders and outside. *M*A*S*H* and *Get Smart* satirized the dubious geopolitical chess game between the United States and the Soviet Union, as well as its pawns of proxy wars, like Korea and Vietnam. As a result of the turmoil overseas, *The Mary Tyler Moore Show* and *The Addams Family* commented on that of domestic affairs, normalizing the progressive counterculture that would become synonymous with the hippie and second-wave feminist movements. When the Cold War eventually fizzled out, an apparent theme of opulence and affluence characterized television,

paralleling the perceived victory of capitalism over communism on the global stage. This combined with a rampant rise of consumerism manifested itself as a time of neon lights and frivolous fun, as shows like *The Golden Girls*, *The Cosby Show*, and *Friends* highlighted wholesome fun to be had at any stage of life. However, other shows such as *Roseanne* appealed to audiences who appreciated the authentic portrayal of the working class, displaying a dissonance between the beloved Americans onscreen and those watching them. Paranoia characterized the new millennium that the U.S. entered, as the 9/11 attacks of NYC spurred the Global War on Terror which was fueled by revenge and fear. A drastic change in the mood of Americans reflected a sense of cynicism and dread, which manifested in the popularization of dark humor and cringe comedy. Sitcoms such as *Arrested Development* followed in the footsteps of *M*A*S*H* and satirized the war, though taking a more absurdist route more in line with the frantic state of the country at the time. As time went on, shows focused more on the growing diversity of the country and capturing its nuances, *Modern Family* and *Brooklyn Nine-Nine* being particularly exemplary. The analysis conducted here does not end, however. History is ongoing and omnipresent, as new world developments force society to adapt. Television of today still comments on the new circumstances that arise everyday, and the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on society (and therefore TV) will soon be apparent.

By viewing American history through the screen of a television, an interesting facet of social history becomes apparent as the nation's most popular sitcoms wield a guiding hand for contemporary issues and norms. This almost-invisible hand uses comedy to disarm the audience through laughter. As their mouths are open, the truth is fed straight in and down the hatch.

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